

**CLIMATE CHANGE IN THE MENA
REGION:
ANALYSIS OF HEAT EXTREMES WITH
GLOBAL AND REGIONAL CLIMATE
MODELLING**

by

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DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY

2023

VALIDATION PAGE

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Title of the thesis: Climate change in the MENA region: analysis of heat extremes with global and regional climate modelling

This thesis was submitted towards the fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy at the Graduate School of The Cyprus Institute and was validated on by the Academic Committee of The Cyprus Institute.

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Abstract

This Thesis aims to assess the recent past and future maximum heat conditions over the Middle East - North Africa (MENA) region under a warming climate using both global and regional climate models. First, I analyze temperature extreme indices in the region for the recent past and evaluate the performance of global climate model simulations using an ensemble of 18 CMIP5 models. The CMIP5 models capture quite well the climatology of the hottest domains and are showing statistical significant warming (up to $0.8^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{decade}$) for most areas of the region. Furthermore, using CMIP5 scenario runs, the projected maximum heat conditions are assessed. According to the high emissions scenario, parts of the region are projected to reach excessively high temperatures ($>56^{\circ}\text{C}$) along with a widespread substantial increase in the number of hot days ($\text{TX} > 40^{\circ}\text{C}$) and nights ($\text{TN} > 30^{\circ}\text{C}$). In the second part of the Thesis, high-resolution downscaling experiments using the WRF model at 24 km horizontal resolution are conducted for the entire MENA region. The WRF is used in order to examine the future extreme heat conditions in the region under different global warming levels (2°C , 3°C and 4°C). Emphasis is given to the compound events of high temperature and humidity and it is found that for higher global warming levels ($\geq 3^{\circ}\text{C}$) several locations across MENA will exceed extremely dangerous levels of heat index ($>51^{\circ}\text{C}$) and wet-bulb temperatures ($>30^{\circ}\text{C}$). Overall, I highlight the necessity to limit global warming below 2°C , since beyond this level, large part of the MENA population will have to deal with unprecedented levels of heat stress.

Acknowledgments

First, I would like to express my deepest gratitude to my supervisor, Dr. Panos Hadjinicolaou, for his invaluable guidance, support, and encouragement throughout my PhD studies. His expertise in the field and his commitment to my success were essential to the completion of this Thesis.

My special thanks go to Dr. George Zittis and Dr. Katiana Constantinidou for their valuable help on technical work required as well as for their advice and support.

I would like to express my sincere appreciation to Professor Jos Lelieveld for his leadership and inspiration.

Thanks also to my colleagues at the Environmental Prediction Department of the Climate and Atmosphere Research Centre and my fellow PhD Students and the Graduate School of the Cyprus Institute in The Cyprus Institute for their cooperation, useful advice and fruitful exchange of ideas.

Finally, I would like to thank from the bottom of my heart, my parents Magda and Margaritis and my brother Vassilis for their unwavering support and encouragement throughout the journey of completing this Thesis.

This work was co-funded by the European Regional Development Fund and the Republic of Cyprus through the Research Innovation Foundation CELSIUS Project EXCELLENCE/1216/0039. It was also supported by the EMME-CARE project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme, under grant agreement no. 856612, as well as matching co-funding by the Government of the Republic of Cyprus.

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Chapter 1

Introduction and Motivation

1.1 Climate change

1.1.1 Global climate change

The global climate is rapidly warming as manifested by the vast majority of scientific literature, while the attribution of this warming to anthropogenic activities is considered unequivocal (IPCC, 2021). According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Special Report on Global Warming of 1.5°C (Allen et al., 2018), the global average air temperature near the Earth's surface has already increased by approximately 1°C above the pre-industrial levels. Until December of 2022, global mean air temperature (over the land) has increased by 1.11°C compared to the reference period 1961-1990 (Figure 1.1). Stronger warming is observed in the Northern Hemisphere over land with a mean annual temperature increase over 1°C in most regions over the last decade relative to the 1961-1990 averages (Figure 1.2). Estimates of the expected future climate change by a continued increase of GHG concentrations can be derived by climate models driven by GHG relative concentration pathways (RCPs), or by the most recent Socio-economic Pathways (SSPs), based on emission scenarios (Lee et al., 2021). In the previous IPCC report (AR5), model projections indicate a likely average surface warming by the end of the century (compared to the end of 20th century) between 3°C and 7°C in most of the globe for a high emissions scenario (Krinner et al., 2013). The latest IPCC report (AR6) corroborates these projections by indicating even warmer temperature response due to the higher climate sensitivity in the the CMIP6 models (IPCC, 2021).

Apart from the shift in the mean climate over the last decades, significant increase in weather and climate extremes has been observed in every inhabited region of the world (Sillmann et al., 2013a; Perkins-Kirkpatrick and Lewis, 2020; IPCC, 2021). In situ observations reveal

widespread significant changes in temperature extremes consistent with warming with stronger trends in more recent decades (Donat et al., 2013; Dunn et al., 2020). The latest IPCC report indicates that the annual warmest day of the year is increasing at a rate that is 45% higher than the overall rate of global warming (Seneviratne et al., 2021). Even a modest global mean temperature increase of 2°C relative to pre-industrial times, could indicate that extreme temperatures in many regions can increase well above 2°C (Seneviratne et al., 2016). Over the global land area, the probability of extreme events currently occurring once in 20 years is projected to increase 340% for a 2°C of global warming (Kharin et al., 2018). In the next few decades, half of the world’s population may regularly (every second summer on average) experience regional summer mean temperatures that exceed those of the historically hottest summer (Mueller et al., 2016). Heat extremes are of high importance to society and ecosystems due to their potentially severe impacts (Allen et al., 2018), for example they are recognized as the major weather-related cause of premature mortality (Gosling et al., 2009; Mitchell et al., 2016). Impacts of extreme heat have already begun to unfold. During the 2015 heatwaves in India and Pakistan the combination of high temperatures and humidity along with insufficient infrastructure caused the death of thousands (Wehner et al., 2016). In Europe, the extreme daytime and nighttime heat stress conditions during the heatwave of 2003 caused more than 70000 additional deaths over 16 European countries (Mitchell et al., 2016).

Figure 1.1: Surface (land only) global annual average temperature anomalies (12-month running mean, blue line) and their estimated confidence interval (at the 95% level, blue shading). Source: <https://crudata.uea.ac.uk/>

Figure 1.2: Average surface air temperatures anomalies from 2011 to 2021 compared to the 1961-1990 average. Source: <https://data.giss.nasa.gov/gistemp/maps/indexv4.html/>

1.1.2 MENA region: a climate change "hotspot"

In this global warming background, the Middle East-North Africa (MENA) region (including the Mediterranean basin) emerges as a climate change hotspot with strong temperature increases and rainfall reductions since the middle of the twentieth century (Lelieveld et al., 2012; Tanarhte et al., 2012; Zittis, 2018; Ntoumos et al., 2020). Global warming is not homogeneous, and several regions across the globe are projected to warm faster than the global mean owing to the possible influence of non-linear mechanisms including soil-moisture feedbacks (Doblas-Reyes et al., 2021). One such "hot-spot" region is the MENA. From the scientific literature it is becoming evident that MENA region is warming faster than other inhabited parts of the world and up to two times faster than the global average (Lelieveld et al., 2016; Lionello and Scarascia, 2018; Zittis et al., 2019, 2022). Climate warming in the MENA follows a differential seasonal response with much stronger warming in summer than in winter (Lelieveld et al., 2016; Cos et al., 2022). In the Middle East, the observed trend of cumulative heat is +50% per decade and among the highest in the world (Perkins-Kirkpatrick and Lewis, 2020). Climate projections indicate that in MENA, heat extremes intensification is very likely to continue throughout the twenty-first century (Zittis et al. 2016; El-Samra et al. 2018; Legasa et al. 2020; Ozturk et al. 2021). For every degree of global warming, parts of the region will record a regional warming of 1.4-1.8°C (Doblas-Reyes et al., 2021).

Even under the current global warming levels, parts of the region are dealing with record-breaking hot weather events. On July 21, 2016, a temperature of 53.9°C was recorded in Mitribah, Kuwait, the third highest WMO-recognized temperature extreme (Merlone et al., 2019), while a year later, 53.7°C was recorded at Ahwaz, southwest Iran. Even in the more temperate Mediterranean region record-high temperatures are approaching 50°C with 48.8°C being recorded in Sicily on 11 of August 2021 (WMO,2021) the highest ever recorded in Europe. Regional climate projections suggest an pronounced warming that will exceed 5°C (with respect to the 1986–2005 reference) by the end of the 21st century, according to a high-emissions scenario (Figure 1.3). These extreme heat events are projected to increase in frequency and magnitude and, according to the high emissions pathway, many areas within MENA are expected to exceed the currently occurring worldwide records (Zittis et al., 2021b; Ntoumos et al., 2022). Unprecedented heat events that occurred in the recent past are expected to occur every few years even for a modest 1.5°C global warming (Jacob et al., 2018), while they will become the norm at the end of the century (Molina et al., 2020; Zittis et al., 2021b). By the end of the century, 80% of the densely populated cities of the MENA are expected to suffer from heatwaves for at least 50% of the warm season (Varela et al., 2020).

Along with the harsh, hot and arid climatic conditions, MENA region is facing pronounced social inequalities, increasing population, human displacement and limited adaptive capacity (Waha et al., 2017; Lange, 2019). The projected warming is expected to challenge social and political systems in the region (Waha et al., 2017) with a great impact on human health (Ahmadalipour and Moradkhani, 2018), agriculture (Constantinidou et al., 2016), cause substantial loss of labor productivity (Dunne et al., 2013) and may also lead to conflict and migration (Abel et al., 2019). MENA region is also characterized by high urbanization levels with a further concentration of the population in large metropolitan centers being expected (Jiang and O'Neill, 2017). Therefore impacts of heat stress will be aggravated considering a pronounced urban heat island (UHI) effect (Li and Bou-Zeid, 2013; Keppas et al., 2021). Apart from high temperatures alone, in many coastal areas of the region hot desert air masses are combined with humid marine air masses moving onshore resulting to extremely dangerous humid-heat conditions (Coffel et al., 2017). Under the high emissions scenario, parts of the region will be exposed to deadly humid heat waves with heat stress reaching and exceed critical thresholds for human survivability (Pal and Eltahir, 2016).

Figure 1.3: Projections of mean annual temperature anomalies in Eastern Mediterranean and Middle East (EMME) (with respect to the 1986–2005 reference period), based on CORDEX-CORE projections and two Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP2.6 and RCP8.5). Boxplots represent the range of projected anomalies for the end of the twenty-first century (2091–2100) based on CORDEX-CORE (RCPs) and CMIP6 data (Shared Socio-economic Pathways [SSPs]). Source: Zittis et al. (2022)

1.2 Global Climate Models

The primary tools available today to generate climate projections are Global Climate Models (GCM's). Couple Atmosphere-Ocean General Circulation Models (AOGCMs) are mainly used to understand the dynamics of the physical components of the climate system (atmosphere, ocean, land and sea ice), and for making projections based on future greenhouse gas (GHG) and aerosol forcing. Earth system models (ESMs) are the current state-of-the-art models, and they expand on AOGCMs to include representation of various biogeochemical cycles such as those involved in the carbon cycle, the sulphur cycle, or ozone (Flato, 2011).

Climate simulations are performed using different scenarios of time-evolving greenhouse gas (GHG) concentrations. The emission scenarios used in the IPCC AR5 are called Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) (van Vuuren et al., 2011) associated with a number at the end (e.g. RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP8.5), which indicates the estimated increase in GHG-induced mean global radiative forcing in W/m^2 by the end of the 21st century. In the latest IPCC report (AR6) the Shared Socio-economic Pathways (SSPs) were introduced, which are based on five narratives describing broad socioeconomic trends (Eyring et al., 2016). Pathways RCP2.6, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5, roughly correspond to SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5 of the latest IPCC Assessment Report (AR6), respectively. GCM structural uncertainty is associated with the GCM response to a given GHG scenario forcing. GCMs have different representations of dynamical and physical processes and thus respond differently to the same emissions scenario.

Global climate models are essential tools for several climate extremes studies on both global and regional level. Sillmann et al. (2013a) compared climate extremes based on daily temperature and precipitation, computed from observations and GCM's and found that the GCM's were generally able to reproduce the historical trend patterns of the climate extreme indices. The comparison by Lelieveld et al. (2016) of the temperature extremes, as defined by the Expert Team on Climate Change Detection and Indices (ETCCDI), for the period 1986-2005 for the MENA region indicated a good agreement between the HadEX2 observational dataset (Donat et al., 2013) and output from CMIP5 historical simulations.

Despite the continuous improvements and satisfactory performance of GCM's, uncertainty about the future climate remains large (Knutti and Sedlář, 2013) and even increases locally with the larger number of models available (Lutz et al., 2013). The complexity of the GCM's results in a high computational cost, which is exacerbated by the requirement of ensemble and/or long simulations for statistical significance of the results (Laprise, 2008). In addition, the current horizontal resolution of GCMs used in multi-decadal climate simulations is around 150

km, which does not resolve regional climate forcings associated to orography, coastlines, and land surface properties and the provided climate output is too coarse to offer regional insight.

1.3 Regional climate modelling

1.3.1 Necessity and use

Climate information at high spatial resolution is necessary to fully estimate the regional and local climate effects of global warming, to perform impact assessments and design adaptation strategies on regional or national level. This is achieved with regional climate modelling. Regional climate models (RCM) dynamically downscale GCM-generated climatic features, to obtain more detailed climate information over a particular region (Giorgi, 2001). RCMs cover a limited area of the globe, typically of the scale of 5,000 km x 5,000 km, with a typical horizontal resolution ranging from 10 to 50 km.

Regional Climate Models (RCMs) were developed in the late 1980s. The idea of using high-resolution meteorological models to downscale GCM fields (of coarse resolution) was first proposed by utilizing large ensembles of short simulations following a well established methodology in weather prediction (Dickinson et al., 1989). The first simulations with RCMs in climate mode (continuous runs longer than the synoptic weather time scale), were driven by meteorological lateral boundary conditions (LBCs) from observations or from GCMs (Giorgi, 1990). This was a step towards modern regional climate modeling and paved the ground for the first multiyear simulations conducted in the 1990s (Giorgi et al., 1993; Jones et al., 1995; Giorgi and Mearns, 1999).

The continuous development and application, made it possible to obtain regional climatic information by applying the dynamical downscaling technique using the output of GCMs over a limited area of the globe. Currently, a number of RCM systems are available and used by many institutions worldwide and the increasing need for their application requires a good understanding of their advantages, limitations, and uncertainties (Laprise, 2008; Rummukainen, 2010; Rockel, 2015; Giorgi and Gutowski, 2015).

1.3.2 The added value of higher resolution

The issue of added value (AV) is essential to the use of RCMs for climate downscaling purposes. The added value of an RCM (Rummukainen, 2016) refers to (i) the improvement of aspects of the high resolution simulation compared to the forcing GCM's, and ii) the supply of regional/local scale climate information relevant to climate change vulnerability and adaptation.

Figure 1.4: Model representation of topography at different resolutions. (a) 500 (b) 50 and (c) 10 km. Source: Giorgi (2019)

The assessment of AV is often difficult, as it depends on many factors, such as scale, regional setting, climatic variable, season, and specific application (Giorgi and Gutowski, 2015). As already mentioned, RCMs run at finer horizontal resolution than GCMs which allows more realistic surface forcings such as orography, lakes and coastal areas, and thus are able to obtain more detailed climate information over a particular region.

Therefore, central to the concept of the RCM added value, is the effect of increasing RCM resolution. High-resolution climate projections are considered as the main tools to bridge the gap between climate models and impact studies, especially in regions characterized by complex topography (Giorgi, 2019; Bucchignani et al., 2018). Regarding the spatial and temporal aspects of precipitation, the advantage of the refined topography forcing was demonstrated in the multi-model EURO-CORDEX comparison at 0.44° and 0.11° (about 50 and 12 km, respectively) by Prein et al. (2016), although the resulted improvement may not be statistically significant after applying specific bias-correction methods (Casanueva et al., 2016). In a recent study, Wu et al. (2020) downscaled the ERA-Interim re-analyses with the SMHI-RCA4 and HCLIM38-ALADIN RCMs at 25, 50, 100, and 200 km over the African continent. Simulations showed mixed results regarding the effect of increasing resolution on the time-mean climate.

For the air temperature and the respective extremes, which is the focus of this PhD Thesis, the added value of higher RCM horizontal resolution should be more direct, due to the refined orography effect towards more realistic lapse rates, but it has not been established clearly from analysis of mean and extreme conditions in related studies. Compared to GCMs, RCMs should ideally be better at simulating and projecting changes to extremes, showing better performance in simulating them compared to GCMs (e.g. (Rummukainen, 2016)). Regarding the effect of the increasing spatial resolution on temperature extremes, the scientific literature have so far provides us with various results. Several RCM studies did not find large benefits of increased resolution (Vautard et al., 2013; Kotlarski et al., 2014; Iles et al., 2020) while others have found noteworthy improvements in higher resolution simulations (Gutjahr et al., 2016; Stergiou et al., 2021).

The MENA region is an area with diverse physical characteristics such as steep orographic and climate gradients, many and complex coastlines, variable land cover, and the presence of islands and large urban centers. Because of all these, climate representation in the MENA region should benefit from higher resolution simulations. RCMs, due to their higher resolution, have the ability to resolve islands like Crete or Cyprus that are not "seen" by the coarser resolution GCMs. Projected changes for those areas can be very different to those over the nearby sea, which makes the use of RCMs necessary. In addition, apart from temperature alone, the current Thesis will examine the combined effects of high temperature and humidity (i.e. humid-heat). Therefore higher resolution RCM simulations are crucial for assessing the concurrent hot and humid conditions whose extreme occurrences challenge the human thermal tolerance (Raymond et al., 2021).

1.3.3 RCM physics parameterizations

The representation of physical processes is considered to be one of the most challenging problems in numerical modeling of the atmosphere and climate (Dudhia, 2014; Giorgi and Gutowski, 2015; Donahue and Caldwell, 2018). The performance of RCM simulations strongly depends on the choice of different physics parameterizations (e.g. of the land surface, boundary layer, convection, cloud microphysics, radiation). It has been shown that the effect of different physics schemes is often greater than the sensitivity induced by RCM's internal variability (Lavin-Gullon et al., 2021). The importance of RCM's physics is also highlighted in Oettli et al. (2011), who show that two configurations of the same RCM are sometimes more distinct than the two different RCMs themselves. The influence of the model physics was emphasized for the WRF model, which is being used in the present study, in a series of sensitivity simulations over the

EURO-CORDEX domain at grid size of 50 km, where the analysis indicated systematic temperature and precipitation biases, linked to different physical mechanisms related to convection, radiation and land surface (Katrakou et al., 2015). The selection of the most appropriate combination of physics parameterizations varies according to the location of interest, type of application, season or climate type since different climate variables has been proved to be sensitive to different model configurations (Katrakou et al., 2015; Kala et al., 2014).

For the MENA region specifically, Zittis et al. (2014a) investigated the WRF model performance with combinations of three boundary layer, two cumulus and two microphysics schemes and concluded that the best performing one for climate simulations over the MENA region at 50-km horizontal resolution included the non local Yonsei University (YSU) planetary boundary layer, the KF cumulus and WSM6 microphysics schemes. Zittis and Hadjinicolaou (2017) have tested the WRF model with different radiation schemes and found that the simulations with RRTMG scheme improve model performance, particularly over the desert areas of the region. Land surface and atmosphere interactions have been shown to play an amplifying role in the projected warming and heat extremes in Europe and EMME (Seneviratne et al., 2010; Zittis et al., 2014a). Constantinidou et al. (2020a) quantified the sensitivity of the simulated surface climate variables to the choice of the land surface scheme (among six different ones) for the MENA and in a follow-up study concluded that Noah and its augmented version Noah-MP were the best performing ones for the region (Constantinidou et al., 2020b). Parameterizations of important physical processes need to be tested more extensively, with emphasis on temperature extremes, and at higher resolution in order to further optimize model configuration for the higher resolution projections. In this PhD Thesis I will focus on the evaluation of different planetary boundary layer (PBL) schemes, since they have considerable influence on temperature (Flaounas et al., 2011; Ortis, 2011; Garcia et al., 2013; Kala et al., 2014) and they have not been extensively studied for the MENA region.

1.3.4 The CORDEX program

An important aspect of regional modeling is that different groups or individuals are interested in different problems or regions. Additional issues are the differences in model setups and simulation protocols among the groups working with RCMs. All these make it difficult to understand models, processes, uncertainties and transfer knowledge from one regional program to another. However, large multimodel ensembles of experiments are necessary to investigate different dimensions of the uncertainty space in regional projections and the inter-comparison of results is important for a better understanding of downscaling issues. From 2009 the global

efforts for RCM evaluation and climate projections (including benchmark model performance, simulation strategy and dissemination of output) are served by the Coordinated Regional Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX) (Giorgi and Gutowski, 2015).

CORDEX is the first effort at full worldwide coordination of regional downscaling work using a common experimental framework and its vision is to advance and coordinate the science and application of regional climate downscaling through global partnerships. The main goals (Giorgi et al., 2009; Giorgi and Gutowski, 2015) of this program are:

- a. Improvement of the understanding of relevant regional/local climate phenomena (variability and changes)
- b. Evaluation and improvements of regional climate downscaling models and techniques
- c. Production of coordinated sets of downscaled climate projections for regions worldwide
- d. Communication and knowledge exchange with the users of regional climate information.

The common simulation framework of the Phase I CORDEX experiment (Giorgi et al., 2009; Giorgi and Gutowski, 2015) follows a certain protocol and consists of model evaluation and projection streams using perfect boundary condition (PBC) and GCM-driven experiments, respectively. The idea was that these simulation streams would be completed for large domains covering essentially all land areas of the Earth (14 domains as shown in Figure 1.5) at a horizontal resolution of ~ 50 km. The choice of this relatively coarse grid spacing was made to allow broad participation by the downscaling community, and the model output followed a common format for ease of inter-comparison ¹. The Cyprus Institute is a Contact Point for the activities of the MENA-CORDEX domain and the work in this PhD Thesis directly serves its scientific objectives.

1.4 Climate and heat extremes

A changing climate leads to changes in the frequency, intensity, spatial extent, duration, and timing of weather and climate extremes, and can result in unprecedented extremes (IPCC, 2012). Changes in extremes can also be directly related to changes in mean climate, because mean future conditions in some variables are projected to lie within the distribution tails of present-day conditions. An extreme (weather or climate) event is generally defined as the occurrence of a value of a weather or climate variable above (or below) a threshold value near the upper (or lower) ends ('tails') of the range of observed values of the variable (Figure 1.6).

Climate extremes can be characterised by the use of 'climate indices' (Sillmann et al.,

¹<http://www.cordex.org/index.php/experiment-guidelines/cordex-experiment-protocol>

Figure 1.5: 14 CORDEX domains essentially covering the globe. Source: <http://www.cordex.org/>

2013a). Some of these are defined as percentage of days with maximum (Tmax) or minimum (Tmin) temperature, below the 1st, 5th, or 10th percentile, or above the 90th, 95th, or 99th percentile, generally defined for given time frames (days, month, season, annual) with respect to a reference time period (Klein Tank et al., 2009). Other indices are related with absolute values in a yearly basis or with absolute thresholds. Climate extremes vary from place to place in an absolute sense. For instance, a hot day or night in the tropics will be a different temperature than a hot day or night in the mid-latitudes.

Temperature is associated with several types of extremes, for example, heat waves and cold spells, and related impacts, for example, on human health, the physical environment, ecosystems, and energy consumption. Heat extremes mainly occur during heatwaves. Generally, heatwaves are defined as a period of abnormally and uncomfortably hot and usually humid

Figure 1.6: Schematic depicting the projected rise in both average temperatures and the frequency and severity of extreme heat events in the future (Source: U.S. Climate Change Assessment Program – SW Climate Change Network).

weather², although definitions may vary according to the heatwaves intensity, duration, and frequency (Horton et al., 2016).

One of the main drivers of extreme heat events are large-scale general circulation patterns and certain atmospheric flow anomalies. A common feature associated with heatwaves is a high-pressure synoptic system (otherwise known as anticyclone) (Perkins, 2015). Recently, such systems are being called persistent highs (Marshall et al., 2016). These high pressure systems occur when upper-level atmospheric winds split due to the meandering of the jet stream, allowing a region to be “blocked” from the zonal jet stream flow, usually for several days (Pezza et al., 2012). As such, cooler air from the poleward side cannot mix with hotter air in the equatorial side, and because of the “blocked” pattern, the warm air builds up. Blocking highs have contributed to numerous extreme heatwaves, including the Russian heatwave in 2010 (Matsueda, 2011) and the 2003 European heatwave (Vautard et al., 2013).

While blocking/persistent high pressure systems are a necessary synoptic ingredient for heatwaves, land-atmosphere interactions are of high importance as well. When the land surface has plenty of moisture, latent heat is the dominant flux over sensible heat, however this reverses when the soil is dry (Alexander, 2011), since energy from insolation is preferentially partitioned to sensible -rather than latent- heat. Therefore, under persistent synoptic conditions

²<http://glossary.ametsoc.org/wiki>

Figure 1.7: Schematic showing the land–atmosphere interactions during mega-heatwaves. Representation of the main soil moisture–air temperature interactions in the development of a mega-heatwave. Red and blue arrows represent positive and negative correlations, respectively. Source: Miralles et al. (2014).

mentioned above, the depletion of soil moisture and subsequent reduction in evaporative cooling may further amplify air temperatures (Miralles et al., 2012). Studies examining coupling between the land surface and extreme temperature have shown that low soil moisture during summer can result in extreme temperatures (Lorenz et al., 2010; Miralles et al., 2014). More specifically, Miralles et al. (2014) analyzed extensively the land-atmospheric interactions and atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) dynamics during heatwaves. As illustrated in Figure 1.7, during multi-day heat events drying soils and high heat advection enhance the ABL growth leading to further entrainment of warm air from its top. This can cause the formulation of persistent residual layers that favour the progressive build-up of atmospheric heat near the surface. Temperatures during the European heatwaves of 2003 and 2010, were found to be significantly amplified by soil moisture deficits. A wintertime rainfall deficit in the Mediterranean region can intensify heat waves over Europe the following summer (Vautard et al., 2007). Thus, the MENA region will be directly affected as climate simulations project an enhancement of the temperature and reduction of the wet component of the system.

The observed increasing rate of heat extremes and the further projected warming raise concerns about the human comfort and survivability across the MENA (Lelieveld et al., 2016) and particularly the Middle East (Almazroui, 2020). For example, Pal and Eltahir (2016), used high resolution climate model simulations focusing on the wet-bulb temperature, a combined measure of temperature and humidity. They projected that extremes of this 'mugginess' variable in the region around the Arabian Gulf are likely to exceed critical thresholds and severely impact human habitability in the future under the high emissions scenario of future GHGs. These concerning results call for spatially refined and physically reliable regional climate model projections.

1.5 Motivation and research objectives

This Thesis' research is aligned to the main aim of the CELSIUS project³, in providing new climate change projections for Middle East and North Africa (MENA), including the eastern Mediterranean and Cyprus, at improved spatial precision and emphasis on temperature extremes. This is achieved by a combination of dynamical downscaling of global climate projections and analysis of temperature extremes. Following the assessment of the available global climate models with emphasis on temperature extremes, the WRF model is the regional climate modelling tool that will be optimised for the MENA region at 24 km horizontal resolution, and

³<https://celsius.cyi.ac.cy/>

employed in the downscaling of the selected GCM projections.

Key questions and objectives of the research are:

1. How accurately GCM's simulate past temperature extremes over the MENA region?

I utilise daily near-surface air temperature (Tmax and Tmin) to derive the indices of extremes for the period 1980-2018 from: i) re-analyses (ERA-Interim, MERRA-2) and gridded observational data (Berkeley Earth) and ii) 18 CMIP5 model results combining historical (1950-2005) and scenario runs (2006-2018 under RCP 2.6, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5). The modeled extremes are compared, in space and time, with ones derived from reanalyses and observations and the best performing model realizations are revealed.

2. How hot are the future temperature extremes in MENA as projected by various GCM's and under different emission scenarios (RCP's)?

Using the same set of CMIP5 models, projected heat extremes over the MENA region are scrutinized until the end of the twenty-first century (under RCP2.6, RCP4.5, and RCP8.5 pathways) with a number of temperature indices based on absolute values and thresholds to describe maximum heat conditions. Particular emphasis is given to the projected highest (maximum) temperatures and heat stress, approaching the limit of human health tolerance, as well as the sub-regional hotspots where these occur.

3. Which is the most appropriate combination of physics parameterizations in the WRF for simulating temperature extremes at higher horizontal resolution?

The WRF model will be applied over the MENA-CORDEX at the, novel for this domain, horizontal resolution of 24 km, and forced by the ERA-Interim global re-analyses data in 10-year runs for the period 2000-2010, by combining three planetary boundary layer schemes. The heat accumulating mechanisms near the surface will be investigated and the best performing boundary layer scheme will be deduced.

4. What are the future levels of heat stress in the MENA region, as projected by the higher resolution WRF runs?

The WRF model will be applied over the MENA domain at 24 km resolution, to downscale the global fields of the selected CIMP5 model data in 20-year periods. Simulations are performed for the recent past (1986-2005) period and for the future, forced by the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 IPCC emissions scenarios, for three 20-year periods corresponding to 2, 3 and 4°C global warming levels relative to the pre-industrial period. The output of the recent past (1985-2005) control runs and the future simulations, are analysed to derive

the change in temperature-based and humid-heat indices of extremes. These results are analysed for heat extremes and sub-regional hotspots, especially in the context of potential human survivability in the region.

1.6 Summary

Over the last decades, along with the general shift towards a warmer climate, significant changes in climate extremes has been observed leading to a worldwide increase in frequency, duration and intensity of temperature extremes. Heat extremes have important human, economic and environmental impacts and associated costs. The Middle East- North Africa (MENA) region, which is historically exposed to background high temperatures and dryness, is considered to be a climate change hot-spot with pronounced upward temperature trends since the 1970s. Climate simulations highlight that heat extremes are projected to be further intensified in MENA and lead to extreme climatic conditions in the 21st century, where in some areas such the Middle East will challenge human survivability. It is therefore crucial to achieve a more realistic climate representation of the MENA region. The overall goal of this PhD Thesis is to investigate the climatic changes in MENA with the implementation of new climate change projections at improved spatial precision and emphasis on extreme heat conditions. The first part of this work is dedicated to the assessment of the simulated temperature extremes of global climate models by analysing their respective performance and future projections. In the second part of the study, the WRF model is used as an RCM and is optimized for the MENA CORDEX domain. This will provide a more accurate representation of climate in the MENA region and thus more spatially refined projections of temperature extremes.

Chapter 2

Methodology and data

2.1 Indices of extremes

In order to assess the increasing heat extremes over the Middle East – North Africa (MENA) region under the changing climate, a specified list of indices of extremes is employed.

2.1.1 Dry-heat indices

The majority of the indices used in this work are based on the daily maximum and daily minimum near surface temperatures (TX and TN) focusing on dry-heat conditions. This analysis is facilitated by a standard procedure that defines a set of temperature based indices, the Expert Team on Climate Change Detection and Indices (ETCCDI) (Karl et al., 1996). The indices under investigation are defined and described in detail by Klein et al. (2015) and Zhang et al. (2011) and can be subdivided into four categories: (1) absolute value indices, which describe, for instance, the hottest or the coldest day of the year; (2) threshold indices, which count the number of days when a fixed temperature threshold is exceeded, for instance, frost days; (3) duration indices, which provide the duration of hot or dry spells; (4) percentile-based threshold indices, which are the exceedance rates above or below a threshold, which is defined, as the 10th or 90th percentile derived from a specific base period. The set of the 12 indices used is summarized in Table 2.1 .

Table 2.1: Set of the twelve, temperature based, indices of extremes, recommended by the ETCCDI, used in this study

Label	Index name	Index Category	Description	Units
TN10p	Cold nights	Percentile	Let TN_{ij} be the daily minimum temperature on day i in period j and let $TN_{in,10}$ be the calendar day 10th percentile centered on a 5 day window. The percentage of days in a year is determined where $TN_{ij} < TN_{in,10}$	%
TX10p	Cold days	Percentile	Let TX_{ij} be the daily maximum temperature on day i in period j and let $TX_{in,10}$ be the calendar day 10th percentile centered on a 5 day window. The percentage of days is determined where $TX_{ij} < TX_{in,10}$	%
TN90p	Warm nights	Percentile	Let TN_{ij} be the daily minimum temperature on day i in period j and let $TN_{in,90}$ be the calendar day 90th percentile centered on a 5 day window. The percentage of days is determined where $TN_{ij} > TN_{in,90}$	%
TX90p	Warm days	Percentile	Let TX_{ij} be the daily maximum temperature on day i in period j and let $TX_{in,90}$ be the calendar day 90th percentile centered on a 5 day window. The percentage of days is determined where $TX_{ij} > TX_{in,90}$	%
WSDI	Warm spell duration	Threshold/Duration	Let TX_{ij} be the daily maximum temperature on day i in period j and let $TX_{in,90}$ be the calendar day 90th percentile centered on a 5 day window for the base period 1981–2010. Then the number of days per period is summed where, in intervals of at least 6 consecutive days: $TX_{ij} > TX_{in,90}$	days
CSDI	Cold spell duration	Threshold/Duration	Let TN_{ij} be the daily minimum temperature on day i in period j and let $TN_{in,10}$ be the calendar day 10th percentile centered on a 5 day window for the base period 1981–2010. Then the number of days per period is summed where, in intervals of at least 6 consecutive days: $TN_{ij} < TN_{in,10}$	days
TXx	Warmest day	Absolute	Let TXx be the daily maximum temperature in month k , period j . The maximum daily maximum temperature each month is then: $TXx_{kj} = \max(TX_{kj})$	° C
TXn	Coldest day	Absolute	Let TXn be the daily maximum temperature in month k , period j . The minimum daily maximum temperature each month is then: $TXn_{kj} = \min(TX_{kj})$	° C
TNx	Warmest night	Absolute	Let TNx be the daily minimum temperature in month k , period j . The maximum daily minimum temperature each month is then: $TNx_{kj} = \max(TN_{kj})$	° C
TNn	Coldest night	Absolute	Let TNn be the daily minimum temperature in month k , period j . The minimum daily minimum temperature each month is then: $TNn_{kj} = \min(TN_{kj})$	° C
FD	Frost days	Threshold/Duration	Let TN be the daily minimum temperature on day i in period j . Count the number of days where $TN_{ij} < 0^\circ\text{C}$	days
ID	Ice days	Threshold/Duration	Let TX be the daily maximum temperature on day i in period j . Count the number of days where $TX_{ij} < 0^\circ\text{C}$	days

2.1.2 Humid-heat indices

I also account for the combined effects of high temperature and humidity. Two widely used humid heat indices were included and are described below:

Heat Index The Heat Index (HI) is what the temperature feels like to the human body when relative humidity is combined with the air temperature¹. In the case of elevated levels of relative humidity, the rate of evaporation from the body decreases resulting in a warmer feeling for the human body. The opposite holds true for arid conditions. HI is defined and used by the U.S. National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) for issuing heat warnings. In this study I calculate the HI using multiple linear regression with temperature T and relative humidity RH as input variables (Rothfus, 1990; Steadman, 1979). The formula used in our calculations

¹<https://www.wrh.noaa.gov/psr/general/safety/heat>

is the following:

$$HI = -8.7846 + 1.61139411 \times T + 2.338549 \times RH - 0.14611605 \times T \times RH - 1.230809 \times 10^{-2} \times T^2 - 1.64248 \times 10^{-2} \times RH^2 + 2.21173 \times 10^{-3} \times T^2 \times RH + 7.2546 \times 10^{-4} \times T \times RH^2 - 3.582 \times 10^{-6} \times T^2 \times RH^2$$

Wet-Bulb Temperature Wet-bulb temperature is an essential humid-heat metric, defined as the lowest temperature that human skin can be cooled by evaporating sweat (Sherwood and Huber, 2010; Pal and Eltahir, 2016) and it has been widely used to assess the health effects of humid heat (Wang et al., 2022). For the calculation of the TW I used an empirical equation developed by Stull (2011) which is based on air temperature T and relative humidity RH, as follows:

$$T_w = T \times \arctan[0.151977(RH\% + 8.313659)^{(1/2)}] + \arctan(T + RH\%) - \arctan(RH\% - 1.676331) + 0.00391838 * (RH\%)^{(3/2)}\arctan(0.023101 * RH\%) - 4.686035$$

2.2 Global Climate models

Global Climate Models (GCM) are widely used today in order to study the Earth's climate and generate climate projections. At the first part of this Thesis, the output of the commonly used GCMs were analyzed. An important contribution towards the assessment of temperature extremes is the generation of state-of-the-art GCM's available for analysis within the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 5 (CMIP5) (Taylor et al., 2012). Analysis of the CMIP5 models can provide estimates for future changes in temperature related extremes, which vary according to world region, emissions scenario, and time period in the 21st century (Sillmann et al., 2013a). For this, the variables under investigation were retrieved from the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) data portal (<https://esgf-node.llnl.gov/projects/esgf-llnl/>) for 18 CMIP5 models. The complete set of 18 models is summarized in Table 2.2 .

Table 2.2: Set of 18 CMIP5 global models with their respective horizontal resolution, Equilibrium Climate Sensitivity (ECS) and Transient Climate Response (TCR) for CO₂ doubling.

Model	lon(°)	lat(°)	ECS(°C)	TCR(°C)	Reference
BCC-CSM1.1	2.81	2.79	2.8	1.7	Tongwen et al. (2014)
BNU-ESM	2.81	2.79	4.1	2.6	Ji et al. (2014)
CanESM2	2.81	2.79	3.7	2.4	Chylek et al. (2011)
CCSM4	1.25	0.94	2.9	1.8	Gent et al. (2011)
CNRM-CM5	1.4	1.4	3.3	2.1	Voltaire et al. (2013)
CSIRO_Mk3.6.0	1.87	1.87	4.1	1.8	Collier et al. (2011)
GFDL-CM3	2.5	2	4	2	Griffies et al. (2011)
GFDL-ESM2G	2.5	2	2.4	1.1	Dunne et al. (2012)
GFDL-ESM2M	2.5	2	2.4	1.3	Dunne et al. (2012)
HadGEM2-AO	1.87	1.25	4.6	2.4	Collins et al. (2008)
HadGEM2-ES	1.87	1.25	4.6	2.5	Collins et al. (2008)
IPSL-CM5A-LR	3.75	1.89	4.1	2	Dufresne et al. (2013)
IPSL_CM5A-MR	2.5	1.26	4.1	2	Dufresne et al. (2013)
MIROC5	1.4	1.4	2.7	1.5	Watanabe et al. (2010)
MIROC-ESM	2.81	2.79	4.7	2.2	Watanabe et al. (2011)
MIROC-ESM-CHEM	2.81	2.79	4.55	2.2	Watanabe et al. (2011)
MPI-ESM-LR	1.87	1.87	3.6	2	Giorgetta et al. (2013)
MRI-CGCM3	1.12	1.12	2.6	1.6	Yukimoto et al. (2012)

2.3 Dynamical downscaling

Regional climate models were essentially developed with the aim of downscaling climate fields produced by coarse resolution GCMs, thereby providing information at the, sub-GCM grid scales more suitable for studies of regional phenomena and for application to vulnerability, impacts, and adaptation (VIA) assessments. Downscaling can be distinguished in two categories, (i) the dynamical and (ii) the empirical/statistical downscaling. In the first method, a high resolution limited-area model (the RCM) is forced at its boundaries by a global model (the GCM), achieving a "magnification" of the large-scale climate fields by a physically consistent regional climate simulation that generates meteorologically coherent small-scale features (Laprise, 2008; Giorgi and Mearns, 1999) due to improved representation of fine-scale forcing

and land surface heterogeneity (Gutowski et al., 2020). The empirical/statistical methods develop statistical relationships that link the large-scale atmospheric variables (Kostopoulou and Jones, 2007) with local/regional climate variables.

The “one-way nesting” technique is the main strategy used in dynamical downscaling and is used in the present study. The one-way nesting technique consists of defining an RCM limited-area domain comprised a lateral buffer zone adjacent to the domain boundaries and an inner domain, as shown in Figure 2.1. The limited area RCM is running for a selected domain of interest for long continuous simulation times driven by initial and time dependent meteorological lateral boundary conditions (IC and LBC, respectively), which are provided by GCMs or observation-based datasets (e.g. reanalysis of meteorological data). The LBCs are applied only in the lateral buffer zone at each time step, hence allowing the model equations to be freely integrated in the inner domain of the RCM. LBCs are typically updated every 6 hr, with a time interpolation to the model time steps, and the ratio between the resolutions of the forcing GCM (or reanalysis) fields and the nested RCM should not exceed a value of about 12 (e.g., Denis et al. (2003). This downscaling technique is usually defined as one-way nesting because information flows from the GCM large-scale driving conditions to the RCM, but not vice-versa (Giorgi, 2019). A dynamical equilibrium between information from the LBCs and from the model equations in the domain interior is what determines the numerical solution of an RCM. LBCs have a stronger influence as we move towards the boundaries of the domain (Giorgi and Gutowski, 2015).

Two essential components in designing the configuration of an experiment using RCMs are the appropriate selection of the domain and horizontal resolution. These two factors are interconnected because by increasing the size of the domain and the resolution leads to a multiple increase in the necessary computing resources required for the run. The ideal size of the domain should be large enough to encompass the areas, where the main regional forcing and processes affect the climate of the area of interest. Increasing the size of the domain leads to a less strong boundary forcing and the model is more free to develop its own meteorological regimes and possibly modify also some large scale climate patterns. The resolution should be high enough to allow the representation of relevant fine-scale forcings (e.g., topography), although the computation requirements for running an RCM increase roughly by a power of three with (for the grid size increase in x, y and for the necessary timestep decrease in order to not violate the Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy (CFL) stability criterion) if the number of vertical levels remains unchanged. It is thus clear that these two factors (domain size and resolution) are in direct competition for computing resources, and most of the times a compromise is required in

Figure 2.1: Schematic depiction of the one-way RCM nesting technique. The figure shows the refinement in topography and coastlines that can be obtained from the use of an RCM. The squared area surrounding the RCM interior domain represents the lateral buffer zone. Abbreviation: AOGCM, atmosphere-ocean general circulation model; RCM, regional climate model. Source: Giorgi and Gutowski (2015)

terms of size and resolution.

2.4 The WRF as a regional climate model

2.4.1 Model information

The Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model is a next-generation meso-scale numerical weather prediction system designed for both operational forecasting and atmospheric research. It features multiple dynamical cores, a 3-dimensional variational (3DVAR) data assimilation system, and a software architecture allowing for computational parallelism and system extensibility. WRF is a tool of dynamical downscaling. Although it is mainly used for weather forecasting, over the last years its use as a regional climate model is commonplace (Zittis et al., 2014a; Katragkou et al., 2015; Zittis and Hadjinicolaou, 2017; Constantinidou et al., 2020b).

2.4.2 Model configuration

In this study, WRF model versions 4.2.1 and 4.3.1 are used for simulations over the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region with horizontal resolution of 0.22° (24km) and 35 vertical levels, according to the Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX) guidelines for the MENA domain.

Regarding the choice of WRF physics parameterizations, I aim to optimize the model by performing numerical simulations with different combinations. According to relevant studies, the choice of microphysics schemes and cumulus convection schemes does not significantly affect the WRF ability for simulating temperature (Flaounas et al., 2011; Ortis, 2011; Zittis et al., 2014a; Evans et al., 2012; Garcia-Carreras et al., 2015). In addition, radiation and land surface schemes have been thoroughly evaluated for the MENA domain (Zittis and Hadjinicolaou, 2017; Constantinidou et al., 2020b,a). I focus on the planetary boundary layer (PBL) schemes, since they have considerable influence on temperature (Flaounas et al., 2011; Ortis, 2011; Garcia et al., 2013; Wei et al., 2017). For this reason, WRF long-term simulations were performed in order to test the model performance to three frequently used PBL schemes. A more detailed description of the different PBL schemes can be found in the following section.

Following recent studies and their suggested combinations of physics schemes, the common setup of the model includes the Betts-Miller-Janjic (BMJ) cumulus scheme (Janjic, 1994), the WRF Single-Moment 6-class (WSM6) cloud microphysics scheme (Hong et al., 2006), the Rapid Radiation Transfer Model (RRTMG) scheme for long- and short-wave radiation parameterizations (Iacono et al., 2008), the NoahMP (multi-physics) land surface scheme (Niu et al.,

2011). After optimizing the model by testing the performance of different PBL schemes (Chapter 5), the Yonsei University (YSU) PBL (Planetary Boundary Layer) scheme (Hong et al., 2006) was found to be the best performing for the MENA region and was used for the climate projection simulations.

2.4.3 WRF boundary layer parameterizations

One way to classify the different PBL parameterizations is on how they approach the turbulence closure problem (Cohen et al., 2015). A closure scheme is necessary in order to derive the turbulent fluxes from mean quantities (Stull, 1988). One type of closure scheme is the local closure in which variables and parameters are defined at each model level and therefore depend solely on local values and gradients. On the other hand, non-local closure schemes account for the whole vertical profile which often leads to an improved representation of vertical mixing throughout the depth of the PBL. In this study I chose three different PBL schemes, a non-local (YSU), a local (MYJ) and a non-local one that turns to local under stable conditions (ACM2). The schemes used are described as follows.

MYJ:

The Mellor–Yamada–Janjic PBL scheme is a local, 1.5-order closure scheme (Janjic, 1994). MYJ is a scheme based on turbulent kinetic energy prediction, and the PBL height is derived using the TKE profile. It has been found that, in case of a less stable PBL, MYJ underestimates vertical mixing leading to shallower, more humid and colder PBLs (e.g (Hu et al., 2010)).

YSU:

The Yonsei University PBL scheme (YSU) (Hong et al., 2006) is a non-local, first-order closure scheme quite similar to the former Medium Range Forecast (MRF) model PBL scheme. Compared to the MRF, YSU scheme represents with higher accuracy the deeper vertical mixing in buoyancy-driven PBL's (Hong et al., 2006). The YSU scheme uses the bulk Richardson number to diagnose the PBL height.

ACM2:

The ACM2 PBL scheme (Pleim, 2007) is a hybrid (local-nonlocal), first-order closure scheme. According to Pleim (2007), the inclusion of local transport under stable conditions improves the representation of potential temperature and velocity vertical profiles. Similar to the YSU scheme, the bulk Richardson number is used in order to define the top of the PBL.

Figure 2.2: Interactions of physical parameterizations in WRF model. Source: Dudhia et al. 2014

2.5 MENA-CORDEX domain

This study focuses on the area of the eastern Mediterranean, northern Africa and the Middle East and in alignment with the regional climate modelling activity of the Environmental Predictions Department (EPD) at the Cyprus Institute (Cyl), I have performed the WRF downscaling over the MENA-CORDEX domain.

The Middle East - North Africa (MENA) CORDEX program is a branch of the international CORDEX initiative ². It was established in 2012, user-driven by a need of regional climate information from the Regional Initiative for the Assessment of the Impact of Climate Change on Water Resources and Socio-Economic Vulnerability in the Arab Region (RICCAR). The MENA-CORDEX domain, shown in Figure 7, lies between 27°W – 76°E in the zonal and 7°S – 45°N in the meridional direction, encompassing the mountainous areas of major rainfall occurrence that feeds the Nile and Tigres-Euphrates and including the water body of the Arabian Sea.

²<http://mena-cordex.cyi.ac.cy/index.php>

Figure 2.3: The MENA CORDEX domain.

2.6 Lateral boundary conditions

2.6.1 ERA-Interim

In the first part of our regional climate simulations, the performance WRF model is evaluated. Therefore the initial conditions and lateral boundary conditions are provided by the ERA-Interim reanalysis dataset and are updated every six hours. The ERA-Interim is a global atmospheric reanalysis developed by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) is available from January 1989 until August 2019 (Dee et al., 2011).

Products of this reanalysis are gridded data at T255 spectral resolution ($\sim 80km$) and on 60 vertical levels. The data assimilation method used to produce ERA-Interim is based on a 4-D variational scheme (4D-Var) with a 12 h analysis window. Six-hourly atmospheric fields on model levels, pressure levels, potential temperature and potential vorticity covering the troposphere and stratosphere are also included. ERA-Interim reanalysis also includes monthly averages of daily means and synoptic monthly averages at 0 UTC, 6 UTC, 12 UTC, 18 UTC of vertical integrals of atmospheric fluxes for various parameters and other derived fields³, (Dee et al., 2011).

³<http://www.ecmwf.int/research/era>

2.6.2 CCSM4

The second part of our simulations includes future climate projections over the MENA-CORDEX domain. For this, the WRF model is used to downscale the CCSM4 model global fields (Gent et al., 2011) of version 1 of the Community Earth System Model (CESM1) (Hurrell et al., 2013). The selection of the CCSM4 model is based on the CMIP5 performance assessment that is included in chapter 3, in which is ranked among the best performing global models for the MENA region and its climate fields used as lateral boundary conditions in the WRF downscaling are bias corrected for climate mean and variability according to Bruyère et al. (2013) and Bruyère et al. (2015). The fourth version of the Community Climate System Model (CCSM4) is a coupled climate model for simulating the earth's climate system. The CCSM4 model shows several improvements over the previous version (CCSM3) including a substantially better representation of extreme events, such as heat waves and very heavy rainfall (Gent et al., 2011).

2.7 Datasets for evaluation

2.7.1 Reanalysis

For the purposes of assessing the GCM's and RCM's performance, re-analysis data were used. Such data sets are often used for model evaluation also because of their gridded format, complete global spatial coverage and similarity of scales represented. They are produced via data assimilation, a process that relies on both observations and model-based forecasts with variables that are directly assimilated in the reanalysis forecast model to be typically closer to observations.

For the evaluations of CMIP5 models two reanalysis datasets were used. The first is the Modern-Era Retrospective Analysis for Research and Applications, version 2, (MERRA-2) (Gelaro et al., 2017). MERRA-2 is created by NASA's Global Modeling and Assimilation Office (GMAO) and is produced with version 5.12.4 of Goddard Earth Observing System (GEOS) atmospheric data assimilation system. The objectives of MERRA-2 are to provide a regularly-gridded, homogeneous record of the global atmosphere, and to incorporate additional aspects of the climate system including trace gas constituents, improved land surface representation, and cryospheric processes. The second one is the ERA-Interim which is described in detail in the previous section.

The ERA5 reanalysis dataset (Hersbach et al., 2020) is used in order to evaluate the WRF output. ERA5 is a global atmospheric reanalysis from 1979 onwards, updated monthly with

a delay of approximately two months and provides hourly estimates of a large number of atmospheric, land and oceanic climate variables. This new reanalysis replaces the former ERA-Interim reanalysis. ERA5 thus benefits from a decade of developments in model physics, core dynamics and data assimilation. In addition to the enhanced horizontal resolution of 31 km, compared to 80 km for ERA-Interim, ERA5 has hourly output throughout, and an uncertainty estimate from an ensemble (3-hourly at half the horizontal resolution).

2.7.2 Observations

The usage of observational datasets is essential. In this study I use the gridded Berkeley Earth dataset (Rohde et al., 2013) for the evaluation of the CMIP5 models ensemble. The Berkeley Earth initiative has developed a new mathematical framework for producing maps and large-scale averages of temperature changes from weather station data for the purpose of climate analyses. The framework contains a weighting process that assesses the quality and consistency of a spatial network of temperature stations as an integral part of the averaging process. This permits data with varying levels of quality to be used without compromising the accuracy of the resulting reconstructions.

2.8 Analysis and post processing tools

2.8.1 Climate Data Operators CDO

The Climate Data Operator (CDO)⁴ software, developed at the Max-Planck Institute for Meteorology, is a collection of many operators for standard processing of gridded climate and numerical weather prediction (NWP) model data. The operators include simple statistical and arithmetic functions, data selection and subsampling tools, and spatial interpolation. One of the main merits of this tool set is that it has very small memory requirements and can process files larger than the physical memory. CDO was developed to have the same set of processing functions for GRIB [GRIB] and NetCDF [NetCDF] datasets in one package.

In the present study CDO was mainly used for managing large files of climatic data (e.g. selecting domains, extracting variables, merging files) and re-gridding datasets of different native spatial resolution. More specifically, `remapdis`, `sellonlatbox`, `selyear`, `selvar`, `mergetime`, `daymax`, `yearmax`, `yearmean` are many of the CDO operators that are used in this work.

⁴<https://code.mpimet.mpg.de/projects/cdo/>

2.8.2 The R statistical language

R⁵ is a high-level language and environment for statistical computing and graphics. It is a GNU project⁶ which is similar to the S language and environment which was developed at Bell Laboratories (formerly AT&T, now Lucent Technologies). R provides a wide variety of statistical and graphical techniques, and is highly extensible. R is Open Source and very useful for research in statistical methodology.

In this study R is used for the analysis of the results, data manipulation and visualisation. The main R libraries that are installed and used in this work are: ncdf4, RColorBrewer, maps, mapdata, grid, spam, fields and extRemes. Some of the functions that are more frequently used for the purpose of the analysis required for this PhD research are: mean, min, max, abs, sd, percentile, kendall, errorbar, boxplot, rank, if, for, ifelse, replace, is.na, rbind, nc_open, ncvar_get, image.plot, map, rect, segments, colorRampPalette, brewer.pal etc. All packages and functions are used to write R scripts.

2.8.3 Python

Part of the data analysis was performed using the Python programming language. Python is a clear and powerful object-oriented programming language, comparable to Perl, Ruby, Scheme, or Java. Its design philosophy emphasizes code readability with the use of significant indentation. I used python for data analysis of a significant part of WRF simulations output (e.g. variables calculation, analyzing 3D datasets). The main Python libraries that are installed and used in this study are: numpy, metpy, netCDF4, wrf.

2.8.4 High-performance computing considerations

The benefits of the regional climate downscaling approach come with a large limitation, which is the computational cost. The long running period (decades up to centuries) and the fine horizontal resolution (some kilometers), in addition to the complex nature of the next-generation climate require the heavy use of High-performance computing (HPC) resources. The performance of WRF model was tested on the Cyprus Institute's recently launched Cyclone HPC system. Multi-core test results for a 24-km resolution 1-month over the MENA-CORDEX domain are shown in Figure 2.4 in which the calculations of simulations speedup and efficiency are presented. The speedup is defined as the ratio of the execution time of the serial algorithm

⁵<https://www.r-project.org/>

⁶<http://www.gnu.org/>

Figure 2.4: WRF performance in multi-core test runs, with speedup derived from the completion time of a single processor run. Efficiency equals speed-up divided by no. of processors.

(single processor) to the execution time of the parallel algorithm with multiple processors. Efficiency is then defined as the ration of the speedup to the number of processors used. Results showed that with medium efficiency (not less than 40%) the model can be run on 200 processors and complete 2 model years (at 24 km resolution) in 24 hours, thus allowing a reasonable completion time for multi-decadal scenario simulations.

2.9 Summary

This Chapter defines and describes the modelling and analysis tools and data included in the Thesis. The temperature extremes in the MENA region under the changing climate are assessed. For this, I define a detailed list of temperature related as well as humid-heat indices of extremes. At first, the temperature extremes of 18 CMIP5 global climate models were evaluated by comparing them to gridded reanalysis (ERA-Interim, MERRA2) and observational (Berkeley Earth) datasets. Then, the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model versions 4.2.1 and 4.3.1 are used as a regional climate model by utilizing the dynamical downscaling technique and performing simulations over the MENA-CORDEX domain. The WRF model is optimized by testing its performance to three different boundary layer schemes (YSU, MYJ and ACM2) driven by ERA-Interim reanalysis. Using the best physics combination climate change projections are produced by downscaling the global fields of the CCSM4 model. Post-processing of the results of the simulations is done by CDO and the data analysis is performed using R and Python programming languages.

Chapter 3

Recent past temperature extremes with CMIP5 global model data

The work of this chapter is included in the following publication:

Ntoumos, A., Hadjinicolaou, P. , & Zittis, G.,& Lelieveld, J. (2020). Updated Assessment of Temperature Extremes over the Middle East–North Africa (MENA) Region from Observational and CMIP5 Data. *Atmosphere*, <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos11080813>

3.1 Introduction

Considering the intensifying warming trend and impact of heat extremes, it is important to thoroughly evaluate the performance of the CMIP5 models in simulating temperature extremes over the MENA region. The analysis of climate extremes is facilitated by a standard procedure that defines a set of temperature and precipitation indices, the Expert Team on Climate Change Detection and Indices (ETCCDI) (Karl et al., 1996). Sillmann et al. (2013a) compared ETCCDI indices computed from observations and CMIP5 model simulations for the globe, and found that the GCMs were generally able to reproduce the historical trend patterns of the climate extreme indices. The comparison by Lelieveld et al. (2016) of the temperature-based ETCCDI for the period 1986-2005 for the MENA region indicated a good agreement between the HadEX2 observational dataset (Donat et al., 2013) and the CMIP5 historical simulation.

In this chapter, we update and assess the evolution of the observed and modeled temperature extremes in the MENA region up to 2018. In the CMIP5 analysis we consider the output of 18 GCMs from the historical forcing runs until 2005, and beyond 2005 from the Representative Concentration Pathway (RCP) model simulations (van Vuuren et al., 2011) for radiative forcing values 2.6, 4.5 and 8.5 W/m, thus extending, by more than one decade (up to 2018), the model

dataset available for evaluation, covering the more recent past. For this purpose, we use two re-analysis datasets, the ERA-Interim (Dee et al., 2011) and MERRA-2 (Molod et al., 2015) as well as the Berkeley Earth gridded observational data (Rohde et al., 2013). These datasets include the daily values of maximum and minimum temperature required for the calculation of the ETCCDI indices up to 2018 and allow for an up-to-date assessment of their evolving climatology and trends.

The present chapter is organised as follows. The analyzed data sets and the employed tools and methods for the computation and analysis of the indices are described in section 3.2. Section 3.3 is divided into 3 parts. Initially, the observed and modelled ETCCDI for temperature are analyzed for climatology and trends spatially, temporally and with box-plots. At the last part of the section we present the bias estimations for the 18 CMIP5 models individually along with their corresponding ranking. Section 3.4 contains a summary and the conclusions.

3.2 Methodology

3.2.1 Global climate models

As mentioned in Chapter 2, daily minimum and maximum near-surface air temperatures (TN and TX, respectively) were retrieved from the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) data portal ¹ for the 18 CMIP5 models showed in Table 2.2. For the purpose of model evaluation in the present study we consider only one (typically the first) ensemble member of each model. The data were acquired from the historical simulations for the period 1950-2005 and scenario projections for the period 2006-2018 (under the RCP2.6, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5).

3.2.2 Re-analysis and observations

In order to evaluate the global models output gridded re-analysis and observational datasets are used. We derived indices for two re-analysis datasets: ERA-Interim (Dee et al., 2011) and MERRA-2 (Gelaro et al., 2017). ERA-Interim was developed by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), and is available from 1979 until August 2018. The Modern-Era Retrospective Analysis for Research and Applications, version 2 (MERRA-2) is created by NASA's Global Modeling and Assimilation Office (GMAO). For both, daily maximum and minimum temperature data were downloaded from the Climate Explorer website². The ERA-Interim data are available on a regular $0.7^\circ \times 0.7^\circ$ longitude/latitude 512 x 216 grid for the

¹<https://esgf-node.llnl.gov/projects/esgf-llnl/>

²<https://climexp.knmi.nl>

period from 1979 to 2018. The MERRA-2 dataset is available for the MENA region grid boxes on a $0.63^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ longitude/latitude 135×69 grid for the period from 1980 to 2018.

In addition, we used the observations-based gridded Berkeley Earth dataset Rohde et al. (2013). The Berkeley dataset is provided only over land on a $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ grid from the Climate Explorer website (at the time of the performed analysis the last available year of the data was 2017). Therefore, due to the unavailability of data for the year 2018, the subsequent calculations and results for the Berkeley Earth dataset refer to the 1980-2017 period.

3.2.3 Data Processing and Calculations

The temperature based indices are derived for the CMIP5 output, the two re-analyses, and the Berkeley Earth datasets. The indices under investigation are defined by the Expert Team on Climate Change Detection and Indices (ETCCDI) and a detailed list of the indices used in this study can be found in Table 2.1. The calculations are performed with the R package `climdex.pcic` as documented at The Comprehensive R Archive Network website³. In this analysis we used the 1981-2010 interval as a base period for the percentile based calculations, as we focus on the recent past (until 2018), which is also possible considering the temporal coverage of the re-analyses daily data.

Since our analysis addresses the MENA region, we focused on a domain that extends from 12° N to 46° N, and from 20° W to 64° E, covering North Africa, Middle East, the Mediterranean and parts of south Europe. For the purpose of comparing indices among datasets of different native spatial resolution, we regridded the original daily temperature data to a common 45×19 grid ($1.87^\circ \times 1.87^\circ$), to maintain a balance between the coarser resolution of the CMIP5 models and the higher resolution of the re-analysis datasets. For the regridding we used a distance-weighted average remapping procedure⁴. We consider only grid points over land in order to focus on populated land areas. Due to the coarse resolution of the common grid, major islands in the Mediterranean, and southern Italy, are excluded from the analysis.

For the CMIP5 data, the indices were derived from the Tmax and Tmin daily timeseries for each model and RCP scenario, and the multi-model averages were subsequently estimated. For all datasets, the obtained annual time-series of the indices were statistically treated and plotted as spatial climatologies, timeseries, trends and box-and-whisker plots (boxplots). For the trends, the slope was estimated by fitting a linear model⁵ and its statistical significance was

³<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/climdex.pcic/climdex.pcic.pdf>

⁴<https://code.mpimet.mpg.de/projects/cdo/embedded/index.html#x1-6230002.12.4>

⁵<https://stat.ethz.ch/R-manual/R-devel/library/stats/html/lm.html>

evaluated by the Mann-Kendall, ranked, non-parametric, test for monotonic trend ⁶. In the rest of the text we use the term "climatology" in the sense of long-term time average.

3.3 Results

3.3.1 Spatial Representation

In the following (climatology and trend) maps we compare the CMIP5 multi-model ensemble mean, combining output from the historical runs (1980-2005) and the RCP4.5 (2006-2018), with the two re-analyses (ERA-Int, MERRA2) and Berkeley gridded observational data.

Climatology Maps

The 1980-2018 climatology of selected indices for the MENA region are presented in Figures 3.1 to 3.4, with maps of TXx (hottest day), TNx (hottest night), WSDI (warm spell duration), TX90p (warm days), respectively.

⁶<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/Kendall/Kendall.pdf>

Figure 3.1: 1980-2018 climatology of the Warmest Day (TXx) for the: CMIP5 multi-model ensemble mean (**top left**), ERA-Interim (**top right**), MERRA-2 (**bottom left**), and Berkeley Earth (**bottom right**).

Figure 3.2: 1980-2018 climatology of the Warmest Night (TN_x) for the: CMIP5 multi-model ensemble mean (**top left**), ERA-Interim (**top right**), MERRA-2 (**bottom left**), and Berkeley Earth (**bottom right**).

First we examine the climatology of the absolute maxima of daily maximum and minimum temperature (TX_x and TN_x, or warmest day and warmest night, respectively) in Figure 3.1 and Figure 3.2. The spatial distribution and magnitude of the CMIP5 derived indices are in good agreement with the ones obtained from the two re-analysis and the station based observational datasets. The CMIP5 ensemble mean captures the observed hottest areas within the region well (western parts of northern Africa and the Gulf region with TX_x > 46°C and TN_x > 33°C). In the northern parts of the domain, where milder conditions exist, the CMIP5 ensemble tends to overestimate those indices, especially over high terrain areas, whereas there is agreement among the three observational datasets (Figures 3.5 and 3.6). This slight warm bias can be attributed to the coarse spatial resolution of the global models compared with the ERA-Interim, MERRA-2 and Berkeley datasets, as the models tend to underestimate the orography and hence the temperature lapse with height. Furthermore, differences among the three

reference datasets are observed, although their biases tend to be smaller compared to CMIP5 data (Figures 3.5 and 3.6).

Figure 3.3: 1980-2018 climatology of the Warm Spell Duration (WSDI) for the: CMIP5 multi-model ensemble mean (top left), ERA-Interim (top right), MERRA-2 (bottom left), and Berkeley Earth (bottom right)

Figure 3.4: 1980-2018 climatology of the exceedance rate of Warm Days (TX90p) for the: CMIP5 multi-model ensemble mean (**top left**), ERA-Interim (**top right**), MERRA-2 (**bottom left**), and Berkeley Earth (**bottom right**)

As depicted in Figure 3.3 the CMIP5 multi-model mean results in longer warm spells over the whole region (with WSDI values greater than 5 days almost everywhere), overestimating the values derived from the three observational datasets (Figure 3.7). Interestingly though, the CMIP5 models capture quite well the "hotspot" areas of the index (with WSDI > 10 days) over the west Balkan region, central Sahara and Middle East, in good agreement with the observed data (although less so with Berkeley Earth). In Figure 3.4, the CMIP5 data simulate values greater than 11 for the Warm Days index (TX90p) everywhere, while the three observational datasets indicate values less than 11 for almost half of the MENA region. Berkeley Earth (constructed solely by station observations) stands out as the dataset with the smaller number of Warm Days, with TX90p values less than 10 days everywhere, in contrast with the two re-analysis.

Figure 3.5: Maps of differences for the 1980-2018 climatology of the Warmest Day (TXx) for: CMIP5—ERA-Interim (top left), CMIP5—MERRA-2 (top right), CMIP5—Berkeley Earth (bottom left), ERA-Interim—MERRA-2 (bottom right).

Figure 3.6: Same as Figure 3.5 but for the Warmest Night (TNx).

Figure 3.7: Same as Figure 3.5 but for the Warm Spell Duration (WSDI).

Decadal Trend Maps

Figures 3.8 - 3.11 present the decadal trends for TXx, TNx, WSDI and TX90p. We compare again the CMIP5 multi-model ensemble with the two re-analyses (ERA-Int, MERRA-2) and Berkeley Earth gridded observational data. The statistical significance of the trends at 95% confidence is illustrated in the maps by the hatching. It is noticeable that the CMIP5 models show strong positive trends for all four indices that are also statistically significant throughout the MENA domain. This is expected from the clearly monotonic positive trend driven by the overall, linearly increasing warming related to the RCPs (evident in the timeseries Figures 3.16 and 3.17). It can be also attributed to the suppressed interannual variability of the 18-model ensemble average compared to the individual observationally based datasets.

Figure 3.8: 1980-2018 decadal trend of the Warmest Day (TXx) for the: CMIP5 multi-model ensemble mean (**top left**), ERA-Interim (**top right**), MERRA-2 (**bottom left**), and Berkeley Earth (**bottom right**). The hatching represents the statistical significance of the trends at 95% confidence.

Figure 3.9: 1980-2018 decadal trend of the Warmest Night (TNx) for the: CMIP5 multi-model ensemble mean (**top left**), ERA-Interim (**top right**), MERRA-2 (**bottom left**), and Berkeley Earth (**bottom right**).

In Figure 3.8, the CMIP5 results show a region-wide, large, positive trend for TXx, ranging from $0.4^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{decade}$ mainly in parts of northern Africa desert and Middle East to almost $0.8^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{decade}$ in Europe, especially in the Balkans. The re-analyses and Berkeley Earth exhibit smaller warming (Figure 3.12), much more spatially variable and in some places of opposite sign (i.e. cooling, not statistically significant, for example MERRA-2 in Iberia and Berkeley Earth over Libya). The three observation-based datasets show a maximum warming trend, larger than $1^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{decade}$, around the Caucasus region. This is may be driven by the positive snow-albedo feedback, which is underestimated in the coarse resolution CMIP5 models with their simplified representation of key snow processes and vegetation (Thackeray et al., 2019). included in the following publication There is generally agreement regarding the spatial distribution and magnitude of the TXx trend in the two re-analysis datasets (Figure 3.12), which is not always in line with the one derived from Berkeley Earth (for example, the latter presents

a distinct warming in south-east Europe). In Figure 3.9, a MENA region widespread positive trend of 0.4-0.6°C/decade is evident in the CMIP5 data for the TNx index, which reaches 0.6-0.8°C/decade in parts of south-east Europe, in better agreement with the MERRA-2 data than the other two (Figure 3.13). In fact, ERA-Interim and Berkeley Earth exhibit similar patterns of warming (e.g. over Maghreb) and cooling (in the south-west part of the domain).

Figure 3.10: 1980-2018 decadal trend of the Warm Spell Duration (WSDI) for the: CMIP5 multi-model ensemble mean (**top left**), ERA-Interim (**top right**), MERRA-2 (**bottom left**), and Berkeley Earth (**bottom right**).

Figure 3.11: 1980-2018 decadal trend of the exceedance rate of Warm Days (TX90p) for the: CMIP5 multi-model ensemble mean (**top left**), ERA-Interim (**top right**), MERRA-2 (**bottom left**), and Berkeley Earth (**bottom right**).

Figure 3.10 indicates that the CMIP5 multi-model mean represents the observed decadal trend in the WSDI index rather well. The GCMs apparently capture the patterns also derived from the three observational datasets. Increasing duration of warm spells (of at least 5 days per decade), is thus evident in the western and parts of northern Africa, the western Balkans and Italy, and the African and Arabian coasts of the southern Red Sea (with ERA-Interim only as showed in Figure 3.14). Similar agreement in the spatial patterns is apparent in the trend of the exceedance rate of warm days, TX90p (Figure 3.11). In parts of southern Europe, northern Africa and the Middle East, a 3-5% exceedance per decade is calculated for the CMIP5 and the other three datasets, although the latter include also extended areas without trend (Figure 3.15).

Figure 3.12: Maps of differences for the 1980–2018 decadal trend of the Warmest Day (TXx) for: CMIP5—ERA-Interim (top left), CMIP5—MERRA-2 (top right), CMIP5—Berkeley Earth (bottom left), ERA-Interim—MERRA-2 (bottom right).

Figure 3.13: Same as Figure 3.12 but for the Warmest Night (TNx).

Figure 3.14: Same as Figure 3.12 but for the Warm Spell Duration (WSDI).

Figure 3.15: Same as Figure 3.12 but for the Warm Days (TX90p).

3.3.2 Temporal Evolution

The temporal evolution of the indices averaged for the MENA domain (land only) is shown in Figures 3.16 and 3.17. Here we plot CMIP5 data for the historical period (1950-2005). For the 2006-2018 period we plot, separately, the high emissions scenario (RCP8.5), the intermediate mitigation scenario (RCP4.5) and the stringent mitigation scenario (RCP2.6). It can be seen that the three RCP scenarios do not result in different temporal variation during this short period after 2005. This is in accordance with the global average temperature projections, where a differential warming due to the RCP scenarios is discernible only after 2030 (Knutti and Sedlář, 2013).

Figure 3.16: Annual anomalies (from the reference period 1981-2000 - shaded area) of the MENA domain (land only) average of absolute and threshold temperature indices of extremes derived from: i) CMIP5 ensemble mean (blue: historical, green: RCP2.6, yellow: RCP4.5, red: RCP8.5). The blue shading indicates the inter-quartile model range and the light blue lines represent the maximum and minimum values. ii) Observational data (black lines, dashed: ERA-Interim, fine dashed: MERRA-2, solid: Berkeley Earth).

Figure 3.17: Annual timeseries of the MENA domain (land only) average temperature percentile and duration indices of extremes derived from: i) CMIP5 ensemble mean (blue: historical, green: RCP2.6, yellow: RCP4.5, red: RCP8.5). The blue shading indicates the inter-quartile model range and the light blue lines represent the maximum and minimum values. ii) Observational data (black lines, dashed: ERA-Interim, fine dashed: MERRA-2, solid: Berkeley Earth).

Figure 3.16 depicts the temporal evolution of absolute and threshold indices displayed as anomalies relative to the reference period 1981-2000. Regarding the absolute heat extremes (TXx, TNx) the evolution of the CMIP5 multi-model ensemble closely follows the warming trends in the re-analysis and observation-based data, most evident from the 1990s and onwards, resulting in a warming, by 2018, of 1°C. Note though that the values presented here represent the MENA averages and, as shown in sub-section 3.1.2, specific sub-regions warm at much faster rates. For the absolute cold extremes (TNn, TXn), the GCMs indicate a warming, in contrast to the re-analysis/observations which do not show significant trends. For all observational data, the TNn and TXn indices exhibit greater inter-annual variability than TXx and TNx, a feature that, as expected, cannot be seen in the CMIP5 ensemble mean, but it is evident in the minima and maxima of the individual model values. In some recent years the observed cold anomalies (TNn, TXn) reach 2°C, which is within the CMIP5 multi-model min-max range and in accordance with documented extreme cold winter weather events in the middle latitudes over Eurasia (Cattiaux et al., 2010; Zhang et al., 2012).

Regarding the FD index, the CMIP5 models follow the decreasing trend in the re-analysis and Berkeley Earth, being about 5 days in the past four decades. Until about 2000 the decrease in frost days although evident, was not flagged as significant in earlier assessments for the region (Zhang et al., 2005), but our updated analysis identifies a persistent trend. Frost days are usually related with night-time minimum temperatures and the FD index temporal variation is indeed mirrored by the one in TNx. It is also worth noting the significant discrepancies among datasets in absolute values (not shown), of the order of 10 days. For the ID index there is overall agreement between CMIP5 models and reanalysis/observations suggestive that we have entered a period of fewer Ice Days in the 21st century. However, due to the absence of ice days in large parts of the MENA region, the absolute values of the index are small and there is a large inter-annual variability.

Figure 3.17 illustrates the time series of the percentile-based and duration indices. Overall, the models follow the evolution of reanalysis and observational datasets. The increasing trend that is observed for warm days/nights and WSDI and the decreasing trend of cold days/nights and CSDI is in line with the trends obtained at the global scale (Sillmann et al., 2013a). In contrast with the absolute and threshold indices, the CMIP5 model minima and maxima are able to capture to some extent the interannual variability indicated in the other three datasets. For instance, the GCM range captures the observed peaks in cold days (TX10p) and cold nights (TN10p), but to a lesser extent the lows in Warm Days (TX90p) and Warm Nights (TN90p), in the years following the 1982 El Chichon and 1991 Mt. Pinatubo volcanic eruptions. The presence of

the volcanic forcing signal corroborates for the MENA region the findings of the global analysis of CMIP5 by Paik and Min (2018), who demonstrated that temperature extremes follow the mean temperature response due to the volcanic forcing.

Further scrutiny of the graphs in Figure 3.17 reveals that while the variation of the model ensemble mean in the historical period (1950-2005) closely follows that of the re-analyses and observations, the upward trend in the scenario simulations after 2005 is twice that compared to the observed warm extreme indices (TX90P, TN90P, WSDI). The observed indices indicate less pronounced warming in recent years and, except for a warm peak in 2010, lie outside the model inter-quartile range (IQR, between the 25th and 75th percentile), at the lower end of the model range. This increase in the observed warm extremes (mainly the TX90P, TN90P, and WSDI) after 2005, within the period during which the apparent global mean surface temperature (GMST) trend appears to level-off, may be linked to sea surface temperature variations associated to the Atlantic Multi-decadal Oscillation (Johnson et al., 2018).

3.3.3 Box and Whisker Plots

Climatology

A more detailed analysis of the climatology (absolute values) of temperature indices of extremes (MENA-domain average) shows the CMIP5 model percentiles and min-max range compared with the Berkeley Earth and the two re-analysis datasets, graphically summarised by the box-and-whisker plots in Figure 3.18. For the absolute indices, the Berkeley and re-analyses values lie within the models IQR, indicating overall good agreement with the CMIP5 results, with the exception of TX_n, which is underestimated by the majority of models. The best agreement is obtained for TX_x, with the CMIP5 median almost coinciding with the compact, observed values (and a model outlier by > 8°C). Note also that the CMIP5 IQR (representing half of the models) for all four indices is about 3-4°C, while the range in the observed datasets is up to 2°C, for which, apart for TX_x, all three datasets disagree, a reminder of the observational uncertainty and the importance of using several data sources in climate model evaluation (Gómez-Navarro et al., 2012).

Figure 3.18: Box-and-whisker plots of the temperature indices of extremes climatology calculated from the CMIP5 (RCP4.5) 18-model MENA domain averages for 1980-2018. The boxes indicate the inter-quartile range (IQR, between the 25th and 75th percentiles), the bold horizontal bar in the middle of the box is the median and the whiskers indicate the maximum and minimum values from the multi-model sample. The different symbols represent the corresponding climatology for ERA-Interim (red), MERRA-2 (blue) and Berkeley Earth (green). Arranged as absolute (top left), threshold/duration (top right) and percentile (bottom) indices.

For frost days (FD) and ice days (ID), the spread of the Berkeley Earth and reanalysis datasets is quite small and falls within the CMIP5 IQR. The observed spread is also small for WSDI, but below the 25th percentile of the multi-model ensemble meaning that most models

overestimate the index (by about 2 days). For CSDI there is overall agreement between models and observational datasets, except for a notable, off scale, model outlier. The GCM median value lies in the middle of the other datasets spread, which is large though.

For the percentile indices, the inter-quartile model range is small for all. This is expected from the definition of these indices as the 1980-2018 range is very similar to the baseline period 1981-2010 for which the average exceedances for the upper and lower percentiles of TX and TN are the nominal 10%. To obtain a clearer illustration of the model spread, the index values for Berkeley are not shown since they have lower values (7-8%) and out of the plotted space. The re-analysis values are similar and lower than most models in the representation of warm days and nights (TX90p, TN90p), suggesting a slight overestimation by the CMIP5 results.

Decadal Trends

Figure 3.19: Same as Figure 3.18, but for the decadal trends of temperature indices.

We repeat the boxplot analysis for the decadal trends of the indices, shown in Figure 3.19. For the absolute indices, the CMIP5 inter-quartile range indicates a warming trend of the order of 0.4-0.5°C/decade for the warmest day and night (TXx and TNx) and 0.3 - 0.4°C/decade for the coldest day and night (TNn and TXn) respectively. These are about twice the rate derived from the three observational datasets, indicating a faster warming in the GCMs than the observed. According to the same numbers, the CMIP5 models simulate a slightly larger warming trend in these absolute value warm extremes than in the cold ones. Interestingly, a larger warming in the warm extremes is also obtained from the reanalysis and Berkeley Earth datasets.

For the FD and ID indices, good agreement between the GCMs and re-analyses datasets is obtained, as all three datasets fall within the inter-quartile model range. The average decadal trend is much less pronounced for the ID index, which is reasonable due to the low average value of this index in the MENA region. The larger overall model warming compared to the observations is also apparent in the duration indices. A pronounced positive trend in the WSDI index, with the ensemble model median trend roughly 5 days/decade, is about 1 day higher than the re-analysis and Berkeley Earth. There is also a negative trend in CMIP5 for the CSDI index (-2 days/decade), slightly stronger than the observed (which is also negative) by 1 to 2 days per decade.

In contrast with the climatology comparison, the Berkeley Earth average decadal trends are in agreement with the re-analyses for the percentile indices. According to the CMIP5 ensemble median, there is an increasing rate of roughly 3% per decade for the warm days (TX90p) and the warm nights (TN90p), although the inter-quartile model range is broader for TX90p. Lower values (by 0.5 % on average) are derived for the re-analyses and Berkeley Earth. The models show a negative trend of $-2.5\%/decade$ for the cold nights (TN10p), with MERRA-2 (and to a lesser extent ERA-Interim and Berkeley Earth), very close to the model median. A negative trend ($-2.0\%/decade$) in the cold days (TX10p) is derived for the GCMs, in very good agreement with the observational datasets. From the overall results of the present section we can infer that the increasing trend of heat extremes is larger than the decreasing trend of cold extremes. This asymmetry has been documented on a global level and it is linked with differences in seasonal mean temperature trends in the Northern Hemisphere (Cohen et al., 2012), which seems to affect the MENA region to some extent (Almazroui et al., 2012).

3.3.4 Quantification of Individual Model Biases and Model Ranking

The overall performance of individual models in simulating the 1980-2018 climatology and decadal trends of the indices is summarized in the “portrait” diagrams of Figure 3.20. The portrait diagrams display the relative magnitude of spatially averaged bias for each index (rows) and for each model (columns). The warmer colors indicate models with positive bias and colder colors indicate models with negative bias. Here the model performance is assessed with respect to the ERA-Interim re-analyses. In addition to the individual models the performance of the so-called mean and median models is displayed in the last two columns.

Regarding the model representation of 1980-2018 climatology (Figure 3.20a), the diagram indicates that the multi-model mean outperforms individual models because some of the systematic errors in individual models are cancelled out in the ensemble mean. For the percentile

Figure 3.20: Portrait diagrams of biases of the 1980–2018 climatology (left) and the decadal trend (right) of temperature indices simulated by the CMIP5 models (RCP4.5) with respect to ERA-Interim re-analyses. The biases are spatially averaged over MENA region land grid cells. The color bar scale refers to the respective unit of each index. Model rankings for each index are indicated with the numbers.

indices (i.e. TX90p, TX10p, TN90p, and TN10p), the models generally perform well. This is not surprising, since for the calculation of these indices we used 1981-2010 as the base period, so we expect values from all datasets to be, as mentioned before, around 10% for that period and thus leading to trivial biases.

For the other indices, most models perform reasonably well apart from some outlying models in the TXx index (MIROC-ESM, MIROC-ESM-CHEM, CanESM2). McSweeney et al. (2015) also showed that MIROC-ESM and MIROC-ESM-CHEM were simulating key regional aspects of Europe's climate poorly. We identify MRI-CGCM3, CCSM4 and CSIRO_Mk3.6.0 as the best performing models. An exception is the frost days (FD) index which seems to be poorly represented by most models. We find that some models show large negative and some other large positive biases for FD compared to the ERA-Interim data. As already mentioned, the ERA-Interim, MERRA-2 and Berkeley Earth datasets exhibit differences between them, therefore, no strong conclusion can be drawn regarding the model ability to accurately simulate this index.

For the decadal trends (Figure 3.20b), the GCMs exhibit small biases for the absolute indices (TXx, TXn, TNn, and TNx). Most models have a small positive bias, in other words, they slightly overestimate the trend compared to ERA-Interim. Similar to Figure 3.20a, the multi-model mean tends to outperform the individual models. For ice days (ID) index, models exhibit small biases which can be attributed to the general stability of the trend and the relatively small ID value of the MENA region. With respect to the FD index, models and re-analyses show noticeable uncertainty, but for the trend most models are in good agreement with the ERA-Interim, except for a few outliers (HadGEM2-ES, IPSL-CM5A-LR). The biases are more prominent for the percentile-based indices. Overall, based on the ensemble mean and median, positive biases are observed for the warm extreme indices (WSDI, TX90p, TN90p) and negative biases for the cold extreme indices (CSDI, TX10p, TN10p). Hence, most CMIP5 models overestimate the average MENA region warming rate, as also shown - in Figure 3.10. A more detailed analysis of the diagrams reveals a few individual models which appear to perform better for these indices. For the WSDI index, CNRM-CM5 simulates a trend relatively close to ERA-Interim, showing a slight negative bias, quite different from the positive bias of the ensemble mean. Other models with good performance in the simulation of decadal trends are MRI-CGCM3, MIROC-ESM and CCSM4.

A correlation analysis between the models' grid-box area and the derived biases for all the indices did not reveal any noteworthy association between the model horizontal resolution and the representation of temperature indices. Only for TXx we find a significant correlation ($r = 0.55$). These results are in line with the global study of Sillmann et al. (2013a), who also did

not find any noticeable effect of model resolution in the biases.

3.4 Summary and Conclusions

In this chapter we have analysed the long-term average and evolution of observed and modelled temperature extremes defined by the ETCCDI for a recent period up to 2018. This was possible by utilizing gridded re-analysis (ERA-Interim and MERRA-2) and station based (Berkeley Earth) observational datasets and output from 18 CMIP5 models. For the CMIP5 models we combined information from the historical runs (1950-2005) and emission scenario simulations (2006-2018 under RCP2.6, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5) and the statistical analysis of the derived indices focused on the period 1980-2018. It emerged, as expected, that the use of the three scenario runs does not influence the analysis of the CMIP5 data for the period 1980-2018.

Results from MENA climatology maps indicate that the ensemble mean of the CMIP5 models reproduces the observed patterns of climate extremes well and captures the hottest areas in the western parts of northern Africa and the Gulf region with $TXx > 46^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $TNx > 33^{\circ}\text{C}$. Due to the relatively low horizontal resolution of the models, and the consequent underestimation of topographical texture, some warm biases occur over elevated terrain regions for the absolute value indices. For the 1980-2018 trend, the multi-model mean exhibits less spatial variability and more widespread statistical significance than the observations and indicates a rate of increase of $0.4\text{-}0.8^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{decade}$ for TXx and TNx .

The analysis of the temporal evolution of temperature extremes reveals that the MENA region follows the global trends (Morak et al., 2011; Sillmann et al., 2013a). For most indices model trends are in agreement with re-analyses and observations, especially the percentile-based indices, for which CMIP5 models capture the observed temporal variations relatively well, including signals following major volcanic eruptions at the end of the 20th century. The modelled warm days and warm nights (cold days and cold nights) continued to increase (decrease) throughout the second decade of the 21st century, in general agreement with the observations. This confirms that in the MENA region, temperature extremes continue to follow a trend of accelerated warming, regardless of the early 21st century slowdown (the so-called global warming hiatus in 2002-2014) in the global mean temperature increase (Sillmann et al., 2014; Johnson et al., 2018).

The warmest day (TXx) and warmest night (TNx) indices increase steadily for the last 40 years while the coldest day (TXn) and coldest night (TNn) decrease at a smaller rate, both in CMIP5 and observational data. Our updated analysis shows a persistent negative trend in the

number of frost days (FD) in the region. Further analysis of processes that control nighttime minimum temperatures, such as regional circulation changes, cloud cover and soil moisture (Morak et al., 2011), could shed light on the driving mechanisms. The climatology comparison is best quantified with the box-and-whisker plots, indicating good agreement for the absolute values (within 1-2°C) and threshold/duration indices between models and observations. The respective trend comparison indicates that for the warmest day (TXx) and warmest night (TNx) indices, the observed trends are about 0.3-0.4°C/decade while they are 0.1-0.2°C/decade stronger in the CMIP5 results. The observed trend is smaller for the coldest day (TXn) and night (TNn) but not for CMIP5 which is again strong. This larger positive trend in the heat extremes than the negative trend in the cold extremes, is also calculated for the duration and percentile indices, with variable agreement between the GCMs and the observational data. In the portrait diagrams of biases, the multi-model ensemble mean and the ensemble median generally outperform individual models, in agreement with previous multi-model studies Sillmann et al. (2013a). Among individual models, the performance is variable for the different indices in the climatology and trend biases, but some overall consistency can be assigned to MRI-CGCM3 and CCSM4.

Chapter 4

Future temperature extremes with CMIP5 global model data

The work of this chapter is included in the following publication:

Ntoumos, A., Hadjinicolaou, P., & Zittis, G., & Proestos, Y. & Lelieveld, J. (2022). Projected Air Temperature Extremes and Maximum Heat Conditions Over the Middle-East-North Africa (MENA) Region. *Earth Systems and Environment*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41748-022-00297-y>

4.1 Introduction

Analysis of projections from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 5 (CMIP5) (Taylor et al., 2012) can provide estimates for future changes in temperature related extremes, which vary according to world region, emissions scenario, and time period in the twenty-first century. From the work of Sillmann et al. (2013b) it emerges that, according to CMIP5 model projections, the future changes in heat extremes will be more pronounced in and around the Mediterranean region compared to other areas of the world, indicating a considerable intensification of heat stress. Lelieveld et al. (2016) used CMIP5 global model projections and derived for a high emissions scenario (RCP8.5), that (averaged over the MENA) the warmest nights will surpass 30°C by the middle of the century and increase further to above 34°C by the end of the century. The maximum daytime temperature during the hottest days may increase to nearly 47°C by the middle of the century, and reach nearly 50°C by the end of the century in the RCP8.5 scenario.

Taking into account the challenges arising from the intensification of heat extremes, it is important to acquire a more detailed picture of the projected changes over the MENA region. In Chapter 3 we compared the ETCCDI indices computed from observations and CMIP5 model

simulations, and found that the GCMs were generally able to reproduce the historical trend patterns of the temperature related extreme indices. It was also shown that CMIP5 models exhibit domain-wide strong and statistically significant warming over the last decades. Here we extend this analysis until the end of 21st century, by revealing certain aspects of future temperature extremes under different emission scenarios and GCM climate sensitivity. Particular emphasis is given to the projected highest (maximum) temperatures and heat stress, approaching the limit of human health tolerance, as well as the sub-regional hotspots where these occur.

Specifically, following the description of the pertinent climate data and the definitions of temperature extremes (Section 4.2), we document their changes in space and time according to different RCP scenarios (Section 4.3) and reveal the magnitude and duration of the projected maximal temperatures for the scenario with high greenhouse gas (GHG) concentrations (Section 4.4).

4.2 Methodology

4.2.1 Extreme heat indices

In order to detect changes in climate extremes, we used indices based on daily maximum and daily minimum near surface temperatures (TX and TN), facilitated by a standard procedure that defines a set of temperature based indices, a sub-set of the Expert Team on Climate Change Detection and Indices (ETCCDI) (Karl et al. 1996). From the longer list of these indices, we focus on the following four, which are related to extreme heat and from the way they are defined, are pertinent to the warm part of the year and the peak temperatures during summer. We also examine the Heat Index in order to account for the heat stress induced by the combined effects of high temperature and high humidity. The indices included in this study are defined as follows:

Absolute Indices These are the Warmest Day and Warmest Night, defined as the maximum of TX (labelled TXx) and the maximum of TN (labelled TNx) respectively, in a year.

Threshold Indices Because of the very high summertime temperatures prevailing in MENA region, we define as Hot Days the number of days per year with $TX > 40^{\circ}\text{C}$ and Hot Nights the number of days per year with $TN > 30^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Heat index HI is defined as what the temperature feels like to the human body when relative humidity is combined with the air temperature and is defined by the U.S. National Oceanic and

Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) and is used for issuing heat warnings. HI is calculated as multiple linear regression with temperature and relative humidity as input variables (Rothfus 1990; Steadman 1979). For our calculations we used daily mean temperature (TG) and daily mean relative humidity (RH) from the CMIP5 output.

4.2.2 Data processing and calculations

The data analysis is restricted to a geographical domain representative of the MENA region that extends from 12° N to 46° N, and from 20° W to 64° E, covering North Africa, Middle East and the Mediterranean (including parts of south Europe). In order to compare indices among datasets of different native spatial resolution, we regridded the original daily temperature data to a common 45 x 19 grid (1.87° × 1.87°) for MENA. For the CMIP5 data, the indices were derived from the Tmax and Tmin daily timeseries for each model and RCP scenario, and the multi-model averages were subsequently calculated.

Regarding the statistical significance of the projected changes in heat extremes, we follow the definition used in the IPCC's Atlas of Global and Regional Climate Projections (IPCC 013b). More specifically, a change is considered significant when its signal is larger than the interannual variability of the reference historical period. We derive the interannual variability directly from the calculation of the standard deviation for temperature.

A simple bias adjustment method was implemented in order to remove any systematic errors in the model output in order to enhance the confidence in the projected absolute values of the temperature extremes. For this purpose, the WFDE5 bias-adjusted ERA5 reanalysis was used (Cucchi et al. 2020). The WFDE5 dataset has been generated using the WATCH Forcing Data (WFD) methodology applied to surface meteorological variables from the ERA5 reanalysis and is provided at 0.5° spatial resolution. Here the projected heat extremes were corrected based on their climatological biases from the WFDE5. More specifically, the multimodel mean biases from the WFDE5 were calculated for the reference period. Subsequently, the projected model indices for the future period were adjusted by subtracting the reference period biases (as detailed in Section 4). Since the heat index is not available in the WFDE5 output we also used the Global Land Data Assimilation System (GLDAS) dataset (Mistry 2020). GLDAS is a high-spatial resolution (0.25°), global-gridded database of multiple human discomfort indices.

4.3 Results

4.3.1 Changes in heat extremes

In this part of the study, we analyze the projected changes in heat extremes in space and time according to the different RCP scenarios.

4.3.2 Absolute Indices

Temporal Evolution

We begin our analysis with the temporal evolution of the absolute indices averaged for the MENA domain (land only). Figure 4.1 depicts the temporal evolution of the warmest day and warmest night displayed as anomalies from the reference period 1981-2000. Here we plot CMIP5 data for the historical (1980-2005) and from 2006 to 2100, separately, for the three scenario runs (2006-2100 under RCP2.6, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5). In accordance with the global average temperature projections (Knutti and Sedlář, 2013), a differential warming due to the RCP scenarios is discernible only after 2030.

For all scenarios, both TXx and TNx are projected to increase until the end of the 21st century. The multimodel median increase in TXx and TNx during 2081-2100 is 6.1°C and 6.3°C respectively in RCP8.5. The warming is less pronounced for the other two RCP scenarios: for TXx and TNx the projected median increase is 1.8°C for both in RCP2.6, and 3.3°C and 3.2°C, respectively, in RCP4.5.

In addition, the ensemble model spread for RCP8.5, indicated with the box-plots, is similar for both indices. A correlation analysis (Figure 4.2) between the models' Equilibrium Climate Sensitivity (ECS) and the derived MENA-average changes, reveals that models with higher ECS tend to show a more pronounced warming. For both indices of temperature extremes we find, for RCP8.5, a strong correlation ($r = 0.8$).

Spatial Patterns

We present the spatial changes of temperature indices of extremes as simulated in the CMIP5 ensemble for all three RCP's for the time period 2081-2100. Figure 4.3 depicts the changes relative to the 1981-2000 reference period for the warmest day and night (TXx and TNx, respectively).

The results generally indicate an intensification of heat extremes with increasing radiative forcing of the warming patterns, which have already been observed in the region, in model

Figure 4.1: MENA averages of absolute temperature indices over land as simulated by the CMIP5 ensemble for the RCP2.6 (blue), RCP4.5 (green), and RCP8.5 (red) displayed as anomalies from the reference period 1981–2000. The box-and-whisker plots show the interquartile ensemble spread (box) and outliers (whiskers) for 18 CMIP5 model simulations of the RCP8.5 scenario over the respective future time periods (2041–2060 and 2081–2100) as indicated by the shading.

simulations of the historical and present climate (Ntoumos et al. 2020). These warming patterns are quite similar for both indices. The changes are significant over the entire MENA, for all emission scenarios. Both TXx and TNx exhibit stronger increases in the northern part of the MENA domain (South Europe) which is in line with relevant global (Sillmann et al. 2013b) and regional (Lelieveld et al. 2016) studies. These results are also in agreement with recent CMIP6 based studies (Vogel et al. 2020; Almazroui et al. 2021), in which similar patterns of warming have been reported. According to Almazroui et al. (2021), the CMIP6 multimodel ensemble indicates a substantial increase in TXx over the Mediterranean region and adjacent parts of Europe, in contrast with areas near the tropics. The stronger warming at the northern part of the MENA domain can be linked to soil moisture feedbacks (Russo et al. 2019) and precipitation deficits (Mueller and Seneviratne 2012), which can amplify heat conditions. On the other hand, this positive soil moisture - air temperature feedback is absent in the arid areas of MENA, since rainfall and soil moisture in summer are practically zero (Zittis et al. 2014b). According to RCP8.5, TXx is projected to increase up to 10 °C over the Balkan region, while a 1-2 °C less intense warming is projected for the TNx index. A similar pattern of regional changes in TXx and TNx is seen for RCP4.5 and RCP2.6, albeit less pronounced as compared to RCP8.5.

Figure 4.2: Scatter-plots of individual model changes over the 2081-2100 period relative to 1981-2000 reference period for RCP8.5, as a function of their respective Equilibrium Climate Sensitivity (ECS).

Figure 4.3: The multimodel mean of temporally averaged changes in the Warmest Day (TXx, left) and the Warmest Night (TNx, right) over the time period 2081–2100 displayed as differences (in °C) relative to the reference period (1981–2000) for RCP2.6 (top), RCP4.5 (middle), and RCP8.5 (bottom). The hatching represents significant changes.

Figure 4.4: MENA average of threshold temperature indices over land as simulated by the CMIP5 ensemble for the RCP2.6 (blue), RCP4.5 (green), and RCP8.5 (red) displayed as anomalies from the reference period 1981–2000. The box-and-whisker plots show the interquartile ensemble spread (box) and outliers (whiskers) for 18 CMIP5 model simulations of the RCP8.5 scenario over the respective future time periods (2041–2060 and 2081–2100) as indicated by shading.

4.3.3 Threshold Indices

Temporal Evolution

Figure 4.4 shows the temporal evolution of the median changes in the number of hot days ($T_X > 40^\circ\text{C}$) and hot nights ($T_N > 30^\circ\text{C}$) per year relative to 1981-2000 reference period averaged for the MENA domain. The number of hot days increases by about 20 days at the end of 21st century in RCP2.6. For RCP4.5 the median increase in the number hot days/year is 37 and reaches 73 for RCP8.5. The multimodel median increase in the number of hot nights/year is 54 for RCP8.5 while is less pronounced for RCP4.5 and RCP2.6, about 17 and 7 nights respectively.

The spread for these two indices is illustrated by the box-and-whisker plots, showing that the number of hot nights can increase to more than 60 days per year. This can be related to differences among models in simulating processes that control nighttime temperatures such as regional circulation changes, cloud cover and soil moisture (Morak et al., 2011). It is also worth noting that for the number of hot days we find a significant correlation ($r = 0.84$) between the models' ECS and the average projected changes over MENA, while for the number of hot nights no correlation is found Figure 4.2.

Spatial Patterns

In Figure 4.5 we show the changes relative to the 1981-2000 reference period of the hot days and nights (days with $TX > 40^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $TN > 30^{\circ}\text{C}$ respectively) per year. The spatial patterns and magnitude of the projected changes are quite similar for the two indices. The strongest warming is observed in the southern parts of the MENA which is expected from the prevailing lack of soil moisture in those areas so that the temperatures adjust to sensible heat only, without any contribution by latent heating. For the more temperate Mediterranean, where the soils are not notoriously dry, this increase is weaker (0-30 days), especially compared to other areas around MENA. Only for the RCP8.5 scenario the increase in the number of hot days is more than 30, over parts of the Iberian Peninsula and the Balkans.

The greatest changes in the number of hot days, exceeding 90 (3 months) and reaching 150 (5 months), are simulated for RCP8.5 in sub-regions near the tropics with relatively high temperatures throughout the year. Smaller increases are observed for the other two scenarios with the respective changes below 90 and 60 days, for RCP4.5 and RCP2.6 respectively. In addition, the change in the number of hot nights surpasses 90 in parts of North Africa and the Arabian peninsula for RCP8.5.

4.3.4 Projected maximum temperatures

We now extend the analysis of heat extremes to the highest projected temperatures over the MENA as well as the absolute numbers of hot days and nights per year, focusing on the RCP8.5 scenario results. We also add to our analysis the Heat Index in order to account for humidity and indicators that are related to heat stress impacts. We now use the 1990-2019 as reference period in order to include an up-to-date account of the current heat extremes.

4.3.5 Absolute indices

Maximum of TX_x

Figure 4.6 illustrates the maximum values of TX_x obtained from the ensemble of the 18 CMIP5 models and the WFDE5 reanalysis. The maps reveal the highest daily temperatures over each period indicated, for every grid point of the MENA analyzed. On the top we show the maximum of TX_x over the 1990-2019 period for the CMIP5 ensemble mean (using the model output of the historical run up to 2005 and of the RCP8.5 thereafter) and the WFDE5 reanalysis. The bottom map refers to the 2071-2100 period as projected by the CMIP5 ensemble for RCP8.5 with the values adjusted based on the CMIP5 model biases from WFDE5 of 1990-2019 climatology.

Figure 4.5: The multimodel mean of temporally averaged changes in the annual number of hot days ($TX > 40^{\circ}\text{C}$, left) and hot nights ($TN > 30^{\circ}\text{C}$, right) over the time period 2081–2100 displayed as differences (in $^{\circ}\text{C}$) relative to the reference period (1981–2000) for RCP2.6 (top), RCP4.5 (middle), and RCP8.5 (bottom). The hatching represents significant changes.

Figure 4.6: Spatial representation of the maximum TXx for the multimodel ensemble mean (top, left), WFDE5 reanalysis (top, right) for the period 1990-2019, and multimodel ensemble mean (bias adjusted) for the 2071-2100 (bottom).

For the control period (1990-2019) the spatial distribution and magnitude of the CMIP5 derived index are in good agreement with the ones obtained by WFDE5. The CMIP5 ensemble mean captures nicely the observed hottest areas within the region (parts of northern Africa and the Middle East with the highest occurring temperatures approaching and even surpassing 50°C). In the northern parts of the domain, where milder conditions exist, the CMIP5 ensemble tends to overestimate the index, especially over high terrain areas. This slight warm bias can be attributed to the coarse spatial resolution of the global models compared with the WFDE5, which more accurately represents altitude induced temperature differences.

Regarding the projections for the end of the century period (2071-2100) the "hotspot" areas remain the same (parts of northern Africa, Gulf region/Iraq). A large part of the MENA region is

projected to experience daily temperatures over 50°C by the end of the century. Especially over the northern part of the Gulf and Iraq, CMIP5 ensemble projects temperatures over 56°C, higher than the currently occurring worldwide heat records (Matthews 2020). It is worth noting that quite a few ensemble members (not shown) indicate future record high temperatures reaching and even surpassing 60°C.

Maximum of TNx

Figure 4.7: Same as Figure 4.6 but for the maximum TNx.

The maximum values of the TNx index (record high nighttime temperatures) from the CMIP5 ensemble and the WFDE5 reanalysis are presented in Figure 4.7. The same method of bias adjustment was followed.

The CMIP5 models capture quite well the observed "hotspot" areas of the index (with maximum of TNx over 30°C) over the Gulf region, parts of northwest Africa and some areas around

the Red Sea. Model warm bias exist over the northern part of the domain, especially in mountainous regions due to the coarse model resolution. For the 2071-2100 period most areas in north Africa and the Middle-East exhibit daily minimum temperatures over 35°C. Parts of north-west Africa and mainly coastal areas of the Gulf will record nighttime temperatures over 40°C at the end of the century.

4.3.6 Threshold Indices

We next extend the previous analysis of single-day extreme heat events to the threshold indices of the number of days with TX >40°C and TN >30°C.

Figure 4.8: Same as Figure 4.6 but for the hot days.

Hot days

Figure 4.8 depicts the average annual number of hot days (TX >40°C) from the CMIP5 ensemble and the WFDE5 reanalysis for the control period 1990-2019 and for the future period 2071-2100. The future values (bottom map) have been adjusted using the model biases from the WFDE5 in the control period.

In general, CMIP5 models capture very well the hotspot areas within MENA. One noticeable exception is the southern part of the Arabian peninsula where the CMIP5 models simulate a considerable number of hot days (> 50) whereas WFDE5 presents lower values (< 20). For the present period (1990-2019) the number of hot days around the Mediterranean is close to zero whereas in parts of North Africa and the Gulf reaches 100-120 days per year.

For the future period (2071-2100) the bias adjusted CMIP5 ensemble projects that the annual number of hot days will reach and surpass 180 days in regions near the tropics and the Gulf. In other words, these areas may record temperatures over 40°C on a daily basis for more than the half of the year. Lower, but still significant values are projected in the northern part of MENA. For instance, the number of hot days in southern Balkans will be 20-40 days.

Figure 4.9: Same as Figure 4.6 but for the hot nights.

Hot nights

In a similar way, the number of hot nights ($TN > 30^{\circ}\text{C}$) is presented in Figure 4.9 for CMIP5 models and WFDE5 reanalysis.

For the present period (1990-2019), the occurrence of minimum temperatures over 30°C is limited to three MENA sub-regions and it is more pronounced (in magnitude and spatial extent) in the CMIP5 data. According to the CMIP5 ensemble, areas around the Gulf, the Red Sea and north-west Africa reach a number of 30 hot nights per year. The occurrence of hot nights is even more limited in WFDE5 with only coastal regions around the Gulf exhibiting a similar amount of hot nights.

While in the present period hot nights are a rare event for most of the MENA region, they will become more common (in frequency and spatial occurrence) at the end of the century. For the 2071-2100 period, the CMIP5 ensemble projects that the hottest areas will surpass 90 days

(3 months) of hot nights per year. Even the cooler areas at the north of MENA domain could record 10 to 30 days with minimum temperatures over 30°C.

Table 4.1: Multi-model bias-adjusted values over the time period 2071–2100. Values are displayed for different indices over different subdomains within MENA. The subdomains are displayed in Figure 4.10. The \pm ranges indicate 1σ standard deviations of the mean.

Domain	Max (°C)	TXx (°C)	Max (°C)	TNx	Hot days	Hot nights	Hlx (°C)
MENA	50.1 \pm 1.4	35.0 \pm 1.1	104 \pm 12	49 \pm 17	45.4 \pm 2.6		
Mediterranean	47.2 \pm 1.6	31.3 \pm 1.3	29 \pm 16	12 \pm 12	39.6 \pm 1.7		
Sahara	52.3 \pm 1.2	36.8 \pm 1.3	130 \pm 14	53 \pm 21	45.8 \pm 3.4		
Middle-East	51.5 \pm 1.5	37.2 \pm 1.1	116 \pm 12	66 \pm 19	47.0 \pm 3.0		

Figure 4.10: MENA region subdomains. Domain A: Mediterranean. Domain B: Sahara. Domain C: Middle-East.

4.3.7 Heat Index

Figure 4.11: Spatial representation of the mean annual maximum of Heat Index (Hlx) of the multimodel ensemble mean (top, left), GLDAS dataset (top, right) for the period 1990-2018, and multimodel ensemble mean (bias adjusted) for the 2071-2100 (bottom).

Figure 4.11 shows the average annual maximum Heat Index (Hlx) from the CMIP5 ensemble and the GLDAS dataset for the control period 1990-2018 and for the future period 2071-2100. Here we exclude the year 2019 due to the unavailability of GLDAS data for the year 2018. Similar to the other indices, a bias adjustment was applied based on the model biases from the GLDAS dataset in the control period.

For the control period (1990-2018), we find that the CMIP5 ensemble mean captures the areas with the highest Hlx. These areas are the broader area of the Gulf, large part of west Africa and some areas around the Red sea with Hlx over 40°C. The models show warm biases relative to the GLDAS dataset, due to their limited ability to realistically simulate humidity.

At the end of the century (2071-2100), the bias-adjusted ensemble projects a strong increase in the Hlx. The MENA-average warming before bias adjustment is 11°C compared to 1990-2018 (see also Figure 4.10). On the other hand, both TXx and TNx indices show a rather moderate increase of about 5°C over the same period. This is in line with global studies (Russo et al. 2017; Schwingshackl et al. 2021) in which the Heat Index is projected to increase sharply in all regions of the globe even for a moderate increase in mean temperature and temperature related indices, pointing to the future amplification of heat stress. Bias-adjusted Hlx is projected to approach and in some areas surpass the 54°C threshold in areas around the Gulf, the Red Sea and in Sub-Saharan Africa where high temperature and relatively high humidity values are combined. The Heat Index values above the 54°C are classified as "extreme danger" according to the NOAA heat warning scale ¹. Note that the Heat Index might be underestimated because it is calculated using daily mean values of relative humidity and temperature instead of relative humidity occurring at the time of the daily maximum temperature.

4.4 Summary and Conclusions

In this chapter we have analysed the temporal evolution and spatial patterns in the magnitude and frequency of temperature extremes, with emphasis on the excessively hot conditions projected for the end of the 21st century. For this, we used the output from 18 CMIP5 models from historical runs (1980-2005) and emission scenario simulations (2006-2100 under RCP2.6, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5). To evaluate changing heat extremes we included a subset of absolute and threshold indices defined by the ETCCDI. The definition of the threshold indices (i.e summer days and tropical nights) was modified in order to be more relevant with the hot summer temperatures that prevail in the MENA.

Spatial patterns of change in the indices were analyzed for the period of 2081–2100 compared to the reference period of 1981–2000. Findings suggest a domain-wide warming for all the emission scenarios. For the warmest day (TXx) and the warmest night (TNx) models show a consistent pattern with stronger warming in the northern part of the MENA, exceeding 8°C in RCP8.5. The opposite pattern is found for the number of hot days (TX>40°C) and hot nights (TN>30°C), which is expected due to the warmer background climate of the southern areas. In the hottest areas of the region the models project changes that exceed 120 and 90 days for hot days and nights respectively, progressively increasing throughout the century responding to the increasing radiative forcing.

¹<https://www.wrh.noaa.gov/psr/general/safety/heat>

The highest obtained temperatures were also derived from the maximum of TXx and TNx according to the RCP8.5 scenario. The accuracy of these projected values was improved by implementing a bias adjustment method based on the model spatial differences from the WFDE5 reanalysis. For the 2071-2100 period, a large part of the MENA region could exceed 50°C during the strongest heat events and may even surpass 56°C in parts of Gulf and Iraq. For the maximum of TNx, the CMIP5 ensemble shows a widespread occurrence of nights with minimum temperatures over 35°C and over 40°C in the coastal areas around the Gulf.

The number of hot days ($TX > 40^{\circ}\text{C}$) is close to zero in the more temperate areas of the Mediterranean for the present period (1990-2019), while it approaches 100 days in the hottest parts of the region. At the end of the 21st century (2071-2100) days with maxima over 40°C seems to become the "new normal" occurring in more than half of the days in a year (180 days) in many locations within MENA. The occurrence of hot nights ($TN > 30^{\circ}\text{C}$) is limited in the present period (1990-2019) for most of MENA. This is projected to change dramatically until the end of the century with a large part of MENA recording nighttime temperatures above 30°C for the entire summer season. Especially, parts of Gulf will exceed 4 months (120 days) of hot nights.

The effect of relative humidity on heat extremes was also considered, in the calculation of the Heat Index. It is shown that HIx increases sharper relative to the TXx index, highlighting the amplifying effect of humidity on the combined heat. Projected HIx index values in several areas across MENA region are projected to reach levels critical for human survival.

In the already environmentally stressed MENA, a strong increase in hot weather extremes is anticipated. According to the high emissions scenario, areas in MENA may have to deal with extremely high temperatures that will exceed the currently occurring worldwide records (Matthews, 2020). This will aggravate the impacts of heat extremes on human health, as limits to human comfort and survivability are being reached. It is thus imperative the planning for adaptation measures that will ameliorate the adverse impacts of extreme heat, especially in the most strongly affected areas of the region revealed in this study.

Chapter 5

Evaluation of WRF model boundary layer schemes in simulating temperature and heat extremes

The work of this chapter is included in the following publication:

Ntoumos, A., Hadjinicolaou, P., Zittis, G., Constantinidou, K., Tzyrkalli, A. & Lelieveld, J. (2022). Evaluation of WRF model boundary layer schemes in simulating temperature and heat extremes over the Middle-East – North Africa (MENA) region. *Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology*. Under review (submission ID: JAMC-D-22-0108).

5.1 Introduction

Climate models are essential tools for climate extreme studies on both global and regional scales. In Chapter 3 we assessed the performance of several global climate models (GCM) in simulating temperature extremes in the MENA region and we found that GCMs were generally able to reproduce the historical climate trends and patterns. However due to the GCM coarse horizontal resolution (grid size between 100 and 150 km), systematic biases occur, especially in areas with complex orography. Therefore, despite the ability of GCMs to simulate essential large-scale climate features, they do not resolve adequately regional climate responses to forcings and their climate information output is too coarse to offer regional insight. The MENA region is such an area, with diverse physical characteristics such as steep orographic and climate gradients, many and complex coastlines, variable land cover and the presence of islands and large urban centers. In this chapter high spatial resolution climate projections are carried out using the WRF as a regional climate model (RCM), and simulate climate over a limited area

of the globe by applying the dynamical downscaling technique (Giorgi and Gutowski, 2015). In particular, the main goal of this chapter is to optimize the WRF model performance by testing its sensitivity to the use of different planetary boundary layer (PBL) parameterizations focusing on air temperature and extreme heat conditions.

PBL schemes are used to parameterize the vertical sub-grid scale fluxes within the boundary layer which are associated with the exchanges of heat, moisture and momentum between the surface and the free atmosphere (Hu et al., 2010; Cohen et al., 2015). Physical processes within the PBL have been shown to affect surface temperatures. Miralles et al. (2014) showed that during multi-day heat events in subsidence regions, drying soils and high heat advection enhance the PBL growth leading to further entrainment of warm air from its top. These processes could ultimately cause further increase in surface temperatures. Several studies indicate that biases in vertical mixing within the PBL could very likely contribute to temperature biases (Hu et al., 2010; Wei et al., 2017; Zhao et al., 2017). As a result of climate change, increasing temperatures and decreasing relative humidity would lead to deeper PBL height in the future (Zhang et al., 2013; Zhou et al., 2020). Garcia et al. (2013) derived, from a WRF simulation for 2001, that the YSU scheme produces warmer temperatures while a different best-performing PBL scheme was found for different seasons. According to this study, results from short-term studies should be carefully analyzed in order to derive the appropriate parameterizations to be used in long-term simulations.

Hence, in this chapter we apply WRF in the MENA region in long-term (2001-2010) simulations driven by ERA-Interim reanalyses, in order to explore the model sensitivity to three frequently used PBL schemes: Yonsei University (YSU), Mellor–Yamada–Janjic (MYJ), and Asymmetric Convective Model version 2 (ACM2). The focus is on evaluating the performance of the WRF model in simulating summer temperatures across the MENA region with emphasis given to heat extremes. Differences among the three PBL schemes are obtained by comparing the model's output with surface observation and reanalysis data and by deriving several statistical metrics. Additionally, we examine the physical associations of those differences via the analysis of relevant variables (such as boundary layer height and specific humidity).

5.2 Methodology

5.2.1 Model set-up and domain

In this chapter, WRF model version 4.2.1 is used for simulations over the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region with horizontal resolution of 0.22 (~24 km) and 35 vertical levels,

according to the Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX) guidelines for the MENA domain¹. The model top was set at 30 hPa. The initial and boundary data are taken 6-hourly from the ERA-Interim reanalysis and were updated every six hours. (Dee et al., 2011). Three different PBL schemes are used to downscale the ECMWF ERA-Interim climate over the MENA region at a horizontal resolution of 24 km, for the period 2000–2010. These are the Mellor–Yamada–Janjic (MYJ), Yonsei University (YSU) and the Asymmetric Convective Model, version 2 (ACM2) and are described in detail in Chapter 2.

Following Zittis et al. (2014a) and their suggested combination of physics schemes for the MENA domain, the common set of the other main physical parametrizations used in all simulations includes the Betts-Miller-Janjic (BMJ) cumulus scheme (Janjic, 1994) and the WRF Single-Moment 6-class (WSM6) cloud microphysics scheme (Hong and Lim, 2006). For the radiation parameterizations the RRTMG is used for short and long-wave radiation (Iacono et al., 2008) as it was shown to perform better for the MENA region than the other commonly used CAM radiation scheme (Zittis and Hadjinicolaou, 2017). The NoahMP (Niu et al., 2011) land surface scheme is selected and has already been evaluated for simulations over the MENA region (Constantinidou et al., 2020b). In the simulations with the YSU and ACM2 schemes we use the Monin–Obukhov surface layer scheme while the simulations with the MYJ scheme use the Janjic Eta Monin–Obukhov surface layer scheme.

The simulation domain covers the whole MENA CORDEX domain as presented in Figure 5.1 and the area that was included in the analysis is indicated by the shading. We have excluded the southern part of the domain since we focus on the Mediterranean area and the arid, hot areas of northern Africa and the Middle-East.

5.2.2 Datasets for verification

For the purposes of evaluating the model output we used the ERA5 dataset (Hersbach et al., 2020). The ERA5 is model driven output of elaborated data assimilation applied on various observational sources and is commonly used for climate change assessment and regional climate model evaluation (Odnoletkova and Patzek, 2021; Vautard et al., 2021). We test its ability to be used as a reference, quasi-observed dataset for temperature and related indices, by comparing 10-year climatologies of Tmax and Tmin with station measurements from the Global Summary of the Day (GSOD) derived from the Integrated Surface Hourly (ISH) dataset (both produced by the National Climatic Data Center (NCDC))². Inspection of Figure 5.2 reveals

¹<https://cordex.org/domains/cordexregion-mena-cordex>

²<https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/access/metadata/landing-page/bin/iso?id=gov.noaa.ncdc:C00516>

Figure 5.1: Map of model domains. The outer rectangle is the MENA-CORDEX domain of the dynamical downscaling and the inner rectangle (grey shaded) is the domain of the analysis.

that out of the 577 locations compared, the ERA5 temperatures are in reasonable agreement overall with the GSOD observations, with a modest underestimation of TX (median = -1.7°C) and a small overestimation of TN (median = $+0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$), thus justifying their subsequent use for model evaluation.

Figure 5.2: Density distribution of ERA5 minus GSOD summer climatology (June-August 2001-2010 average) for maximum (left) and minimum (right) temperature.

5.2.3 Bias analysis and indices

We assess the performance of the WRF model employing the three different PBL schemes with emphasis on the heat extremes. Since we focus on the simulated hot conditions across

MENA, the June–July–August climatologies of the maximum (TX) and minimum temperature (TN) have been analyzed. For the heat extremes we consider the warmest day (TXx) and warmest night (TNx), which are among the indicators proposed by the Expert Team on Climate Change Detection and Indices (ETCCDI) (Karl et al., 1996). We also test the model’s ability to capture humid heat conditions (combination of high temperature and humidity) through the calculation of the Heat Index (HI). Following the method used in a previous work (Ntoumos et al., 2022), the HI is calculated via a multiple linear regression with temperature and relative humidity as input variables (Rothfus, 1990; Steadman, 1979). The simulated climate deviations from the observed conditions were studied through the analysis of bias maps calculated from the average 2001-2010 values. The model validation is not limited to the analysis of common surface variables (such as the 2-m temperature) but it is enhanced with additional variables such as specific humidity and PBL height (PBLH) in an effort to explain the temperature biases. We also derive vertical profiles of potential temperature and specific humidity for selected areas of interest in order to explore in detail the differences among the three PBL schemes.

5.2.4 Evaluation Metrics

In order to quantitatively assess the performance of each simulation, we used a number of statistical metrics using monthly values for TX and TN and annual values for the indices of extremes from the model output and the gridded observational data. A short description of each metric is presented below:

Mean Absolute Error (MAE) It is used to describe the average model performance error. This metric has some advantages over the widely used Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) (Willmott and Matsuura, 2005). According to that study RMSE tends to become increasingly larger than MAE as the distribution of error magnitudes becomes more variable.

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |SIM_i - OBS_i| \quad (1)$$

The Modified Index of Agreement (MIA) It is a standardized measure of the degree of the model prediction error. This index varies between 0 and 1. It was introduced by Willmott (1981) and refined by Legates and McCabe Jr (1999).

$$MIA = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (OBS_i - SIM_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (|SIM_i - \overline{OBS}| + |OBS_i - \overline{OBS}|)^2} \quad (2)$$

Error in the standard deviation (STDE) The error in the standard deviation (STDE) (Zittis et al., 2014a) of the two samples (monthly OBS and SIM) to explore if the modeled variability realistically represents that of the observations.

$$STDE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |\sigma_{OBS_i} - \sigma_{SIM_i}| \quad (3)$$

5.3 Results

5.3.1 Summer maximum and minimum temperature

Figure 5.3: ERA5 summer mean maximum temperature (top left) and absolute biases of the 3 simulations with different PBL schemes relative to the ERA5 dataset averaged over the period 2001-2010.

Figure 5.3 shows the WRF biases for each PBL scheme for the summer maximum temperature relative to the ERA5 dataset. The model biases strongly vary according to geographic location. All schemes exhibit warm biases in most areas of the MENA region and particularly over the Middle East and north-east Africa where they overpredict maximum temperature by 2°C - 4°C , depending on the scheme used. This was also found in other RCM studies over the MENA domain (Bucchignani et al., 2016; Zittis and Hadjinicolaou, 2017; Fonseca et al., 2020; Branch et al., 2021) which have shown similar warm biases for TX in these areas. They suggest that these biases are associated with a combination of model deficiencies such as overestimation of downwelling surface SW radiation, underestimation of albedo and unrealistic cloud cover. In our case we found an underestimation of the albedo value (Figure 5.4) in most of North Africa and the Middle East which is around 0.2 while in ERA5 reanalysis it is around 0.4.

It is clear that ACM2 is the warmest scheme, mainly in sub-Saharan Africa and the Mediterranean, where the other two schemes show opposite sign biases. MYJ predicts significantly lower temperatures in parts of sub-Saharan Africa and, on the contrary, has strong warm biases (over 5°C) in north-East Africa and the Middle-East. The same pattern is obtained for the YSU scheme although it shows weaker biases than MYJ. Overall, the YSU scheme seems to be in better agreement with ERA5 which is also confirmed with the following quantitative assessment (section 5.3.3).

In a similar way, the ERA5 mean minimum temperature and the respective WRF PBL scheme biases are presented in Figure 5.5. Like before, the sign and magnitude of model biases strongly vary according to geographic location with all schemes predicting colder temperatures in most of Middle-East while differences are observed in North Africa region. In contrast with maximum temperatures in which warm biases prevail, for the minimum temperatures the WRF runs tend to be colder in many areas and especially in the Arabian peninsula where cold biases exceed 5°C in the ACM2 scheme. Such nocturnal biases in these areas have been noted in previous analyses (Branch et al., 2014; Zittis et al., 2014a; Fekih and Mohamed, 2019; Weston et al., 2019). Fonseca et al. (2020) found that cold biases in arid regions are associated with a lower downward flux of longwave radiation, in a comparison with radiation measurements. Analysis of nighttime downward LW radiation (Figure 5.6) shows that the ACM2 scheme underestimates the LW radiation particularly in the arid areas, consistent with the observed cold bias. Regarding the other two schemes, both predict weaker cold bias, showing a better performance overall.

Figure 5.4: ERA5 mean albedo values (top left) and absolute biases of the three WRF simulations relative to the ERA5 dataset averaged over the period 2001-2010

Figure 5.5: Same as Figure 5.3 but for the summer mean minimum temperature.

Figure 5.6: ERA5 summer mean downward longwave radiation at 00:00 UTC (top left) and absolute biases of the three WRF simulations relative to the ERA5 dataset averaged over the period 2001-2010.

Figure 5.7: Same as Figure 5.3 but for the Warmest Day (TXx).

5.3.2 Heat extremes

In this part of the chapter, we analyze the sensitivity of the different PBL schemes in simulating heat extremes.

Figure 5.7 depicts the ERA5 mean values and the absolute biases of the different schemes for the warmest day of the year (TXx) index. A first look at model results indicates a warm bias in all simulations that has already been seen in the summer mean TX (Figure 5.3). Here the biases tend to be more uniform with WRF predicting higher values for most of the MENA region and with magnitude exceeding 8°C in a few locations. Larger biases are found in areas with more complex orography or different land surface characteristics (Nile Delta) and could be related to the performance of the land surface scheme (Constantinidou et al., 2020b). Spots with cold biases can be found mainly in mountainous, temperate areas in the northern part of the domain. These cold biases are not present in the ACM2 simulation which is much warmer

Figure 5.8: Same as Figure 5.3 but for the Warmest Night (TNx).

in the Mediterranean region, especially in the coastal areas. The MYJ scheme, on the other hand, exhibits substantial warm biases in the whole eastern part of the domain. In the southern part of the region a general agreement is found for the three PBL schemes in contrast with summer maximum temperatures, which is attributed to the computation of the TXx index that accounts for temperature all year round. The southern part of our study domain is influenced by the seasonal march of temperature in the tropics with the annual maximum not necessarily recorded in the summer months.

Regarding the warmest night (TNx) index (Figure 5.8), the model biases differ notably among the PBL schemes and geographic locations. The WRF model produces cold biases in many areas (in contrast with TXx) which is expected from the analysis of TN. Especially in the eastern part of the domain (Middle East and Anatolia) all schemes underestimate the TNx index. For ACM2 the largest cold biases are obtained in the arid areas (Sahara and Middle

Figure 5.9: Same as Figure 5.3 but for the maximum of Heat Index (Hix).

East) exceeding 6°C (e.g. in Saudi Arabia). On the other hand, in southern Europe the ACM2 is again the warmest scheme simulating higher TNx index mainly in the Balkans. YSU and MYJ are performing better in the Middle East showing weaker biases while they are quite warmer in North Africa with the YSU being the warmest. In southern Europe both schemes are in good agreement with ERA5.

Apart from the temperature-based indices, the Heat Index (HI) is also examined in order to account for the effect of humidity. For our calculations, we used hourly data of temperature and relative humidity (RH) from the ERA5 reanalysis and WRF output. The main results for the annual maximum of HI (Hix) are illustrated in Figure 5.9.

A different spatial distribution of biases is evident compared to the analysis of indices that depend solely on temperature. These differences can be attributed to the humidity patterns as shown in section 5.3.4 with the MYJ scheme being the wettest while the ACM2 being the driest scheme. Therefore we note that MYJ simulates much higher Hix in the arid areas of the region (Sahara and Middle East) with warm biases approaching 10°C in locations over north-east Africa. On the other hand, the ACM2 simulation predicts colder Hix in many arid areas (e.g

Table 5.1: Statistical metrics for maximum (TX), minimum (TN) temperature, warmest day (TXx), warmest night (TNx) and maximum of Heat Index (HIx) for the WRF simulations with the three PBL schemes (YSU, MYJ, ACM2) averaged over the MENA domain. The ones indicating best performance (with smallest MAE and STDE and largest MIA) are in bold.

Variable	Metric	YSU	MYJ	ACM2
TX	MAE	2.15	2.55	3.03
	STDE	0.79	0.92	0.44
	MIA	0.78	0.74	0.70
TN	MAE	1.74	2.16	2.77
	STDE	0.44	0.33	0.19
	MIA	0.78	0.72	0.64
TXx	MAE	2.83	2.98	2.85
	STDE	0.68	0.95	0.16
	MIA	0.69	0.66	0.67
TNx	MAE	1.75	2.17	2.85
	STDE	0.21	0.18	0.46
	MIA	0.76	0.70	0.66
HIx	MAE	1.91	2.64	1.5
	STDE	0.38	0.97	0.45
	MIA	0.74	0.67	0.76

Gulf region) showing better performance over the Sahara desert with small biases from the ERA5. In the YSU scheme, the spatial patterns of biases, albeit weaker, are in agreement with the ones in MYJ. For the more temperate Mediterranean areas, MYJ and YSU show slightly lower HIx on average, while the ACM2 is warmer, resembling the patterns apparent in TX and TXx.

5.3.3 Statistical evaluation

The different statistical metrics described in the methodology section were applied to all grid points of the analysis domain for the model output and the ERA5 and their MENA domain average values are presented in Table 5.1. For the summer TX and TN, the YSU scheme

Table 5.2: Percentage of gridpoints with MAE < 1 relative to the ERA5. The best performing scheme for each variable is in bold.

PBL scheme	TX	TN	TXx	TNx	Hlx
YSU	30	40	13	42	37
MYJ	26	25	12	27	21
ACM2	12	16	13	28	45

has the best performance mainly according to MAE and MIA and the ACM2 it is the worst performing, confirming the main points of the previous visual analysis. A similar performance is evident in the TNx index while for the TXx index the differences in the metrics among the three schemes are smaller. This can be attributed to the larger errors of the YSU in the Middle-East comparing to ACM2 which performs better. Regarding the Hlx index, the ACM2 performs best in MAE and MIA, in contrast to its lowest scores for those metrics in all other variables. The ACM2 includes the lowest errors in standard deviation for all variables (apart from Hlx) indicating a better representation of the observed inter-annual variability relative to the other two schemes.

Table 5.2 shows the percentage of gridpoints of the analysis domain with a good agreement (MAE < 1) between ERA5 and WRF simulations for each scheme. Regarding the TX and TN, the YSU scheme appears to be the best performing while ACM2 performs the worst. For YSU scheme, the percentage of low bias gridpoints reaches 30% and 40% for TX and TN respectively. The same pattern is observed for the TNx index, while for the TXx index all schemes are presenting low values of good performing gridpoints. Similar to Table 5.1 the ACM2 simulation seems to be in better agreement with ERA5 for the Hlx index. However, since the Heat Index is a combination of two variables (temperature and relative humidity), the model may provide the right average value for the wrong reason, as a result of a compensation of errors.

5.3.4 Specific humidity

We next expand our analysis with additional variables in order to support interpretation of the previous results. Figure 5.10 shows the summer climatology of surface specific humidity (top left) as well as the biases of each scheme compared to ERA5.

The ERA5 map shows an expected spatial distribution of specific humidity with very low values (< 6 g/kg) over the Sahara desert and the Middle East and higher values (8-10 g/kg) around

Figure 5.10: ERA5 summer mean specific humidity (top left) and absolute biases of the 3 simulations with different PBL schemes relative to the ERA5 dataset averaged over the period 2001-2010.

the Mediterranean and particularly in sub-Saharan Africa ($> 10 \text{ g/kg}$). The largest discrepancies among the three schemes appear around sub-Saharan Africa where MYJ overestimates specific humidity while the opposite is true for the ACM2 scheme. The YSU biases are moderate and in better agreement with ERA5. MYJ is also the moistest scheme in other areas like southern Europe where exhibits weak wet biases and, on the other hand, ACM2 seems to be the driest scheme.

These wet biases of the MYJ scheme are in line with previous studies which indicate that the MYJ simulations were overestimating surface specific humidity (Hu et al., 2010; Garcia et al., 2013; Avolio et al., 2017). As a local closure scheme, MYJ produces weaker vertical mixing (Brown, 1996) compared to the non-local YSU and ACM2 schemes and therefore entrains less warmer and drier air into the PBL. Furthermore, the large differences in surface moisture derived for sub-Saharan Africa can be linked to the model representation of the West African Monsoon (WAM) patterns. Klein et al. (2015) showed that the choice of the PBL scheme strongly affects the position of the WAM rainband with a southward shift in ACM2 scheme and a northward shift in the MYJ scheme. This is consistent with the moisture and maximum temperature biases in the current study. In the following sections, we will further investigate the entrainment processes within the PBL via the estimation of PBL thickness and vertical profiles.

5.3.5 PBL height

One way to further investigate the physical mechanisms related to the temperature biases is via the estimation of the PBL height (PBLH). According to relevant studies PBLH could contribute to model temperature biases (Hu et al., 2010; Garcia et al., 2013; Wei et al., 2017), as it is considered a good indicator of the degree of the thermally induced turbulent mixing and entrainment (Stull, 1988). Generally, weaker vertical mixing hinders PBL growth and produces insufficient entrainment of warmer and drier free-tropospheric air into the PBL which leads to cold and moist PBLs. The opposite situation holds true for the regions with warmer and drier PBLs.

Usually the transition from the PBL to the free atmosphere can be distinguished by a significant change in temperature and water vapor and, therefore the simplest approach for the PBLH estimation is to identify where the greatest change occurs in the vertical profile. Following Hu et al. (2010) and Garcia et al. (2013), we use the 1.5-theta-increase method which defines PBL heights as the level at which the potential temperature first exceeds the minimum potential temperature within the boundary layer by 1.5 K (Nielsen-Gammon et al., 2008). This method is favoured among others, especially for well-developed mixed layers which is the case

Figure 5.11: ERA5 summer mean PBL height (top left) at 12:00 UTC and absolute biases of the 3 simulations with different PBL schemes relative to the ERA5 dataset averaged over the period 2001-2010.

in our domain during summer days (Garcia-Carreras et al., 2015; Zhou et al., 2020).

Figure 5.11 shows PBLH maps for the three summer months at 12:00 UTC, approximately at the formation of the deep daytime mixed layer. The ERA5 climatology map (top left) shows the deepest PBLs (up to 5km) in the Middle East and parts of the Sahara desert, consistent with relevant studies showing that PBLH can stretch over 4km in daytime in these areas (Gamo, 1996; Marsham et al., 2008). All schemes are simulating deeper PBLs compared to ERA5 in the northern parts of Africa and in the Middle East which is consistent with the warm biases that are observed in these areas (Figure 5.3). Large discrepancies can be found in the southern parts of the Sahara and the sub-Saharan Africa where ACM2 overestimates the PBLH while the other two schemes predicting lower PBLH. Also in southern Europe ACM2 is predicting the highest and MYJ the lowest PBLH. This supports the hypothesis that temperature biases are related to differences in vertical mixing strength and entrainment. However, in the parts of the Middle-East, ACM2 is predicting deeper PBL while showing weaker warm biases comparing with the other two. An analysis of surface sensible heat flux values (Figure 5.12) does not show any difference between the three schemes in these areas and could in part explain this inconsistency.

5.3.6 Vertical profiles

In order to obtain a more detailed view of the behaviour of the different PBL schemes and further investigate entrainment processes, the vertical profiles of temperature and moisture have been analysed.

Figures 5.13 and 5.14 show the 2001-2010 climatology profiles of potential temperature, which has already been used for the PBLH estimation, and specific humidity for four different locations with different climate types and land surface characteristics. All profiles show averaged values for the summer months during daytime at 12:00 UTC. Colour lines represent the three different WRF simulations and dots the ERA5 values.

More specifically, vertical profiles of Figure 5.13 refer to locations in central Italy (left) and in sub-Saharan Africa (right). Profiles with colder conditions near the surface predict higher moisture as well. Among the three schemes, the MYJ, a local closure scheme, predicts the lower temperature and higher moisture at the lowest levels. Local closure schemes are reported to underestimate vertical mixing in the convective boundary layer (Brown, 1996) thus providing less efficient transport of water vapour to higher levels along with a weaker entrainment of warm and dry air from the free troposphere. In the case of central Italy profiles, both the ERA5 and MYJ scheme show larger values of moisture near the surface while they exhibit less moisture

Figure 5.12: ERA5 summer mean sensible heat at 12:00 UTC (top left) and absolute biases of the three WRF simulations relative to the ERA5 dataset averaged over the period 2001-2010.

Figure 5.13: Mean profiles of (top) temperature and (bottom) moisture at 12:00 UTC for the summer months (JJA) and for land locations in central Mediterranean and sub-Saharan.

aloft. On the other hand, the YSU and ACM2 schemes are much drier and warmer in the lower troposphere in line with other studies (Hu et al., 2010; Garcia et al., 2013) which find that non-local schemes tend to entrain warmer and drier air into the PBL. Profiles in the sub-Saharan Africa show larger discrepancies in the three schemes from the ERA5 reanalysis. The ACM2 scheme simulates much warmer and drier conditions than the ERA5, indicative of much stronger vertical mixing, as also demonstrated with the overestimation of PBL thickness in those areas (Fig. 5.11).

Figure 5.14 depicts the mean profiles for locations in Saudi Arabia (left) and the Cairo area (right). A pattern different from the one in Figure 5.13 is apparent here, with the colder profiles not being the wettest ones and vice versa. As shown in the potential temperature profiles for the Cairo area, MYJ is the warmest among the three schemes while it predicts more moisture than the other two schemes. All three parameterizations predict warmer temperatures and more moisture than the ERA5 below 2000 meters implying a common cause for this bias. ERA5 shows more moisture near the surface while being drier in the higher levels which indicates

Figure 5.14: Same as Fig. 5.13 but for two locations in the Middle East.

weaker heat and moisture vertical transport compared to the WRF simulations. This could be related to land surface characteristics around the Nile Delta. This is evident from the latent heat flux maps (Figure 5.15), in which WRF simulations show quite lower values of latent heat flux around the Nile Delta compared to ERA5, implying reduced evaporation from the surface. In Saudi Arabian profiles, ACM2 is the driest despite being the coldest among the three schemes. As illustrated in Figure 5.11, ACM2 also predicts the highest PBL during daytime suggesting more entrainment of warmer and drier air into the PBL.

5.4 Summary and Conclusions

We have performed and analyzed RCM simulations (2001-2010) for the MENA-CORDEX domain in order to assess the performance of three PBL schemes employed (MYJ, YSU, and ACM2) for climate applications focusing on surface air temperature and temperature extremes. For this, the WRF model was applied at 24 km resolution and driven by the ERA Interim re-analysis. For the evaluation of the WRF runs we used related meteorological variables from

Figure 5.15: ERA5 summer mean latent heat at 12:00 UTC (top left) and absolute biases of the three WRF simulations relative to the ERA5 dataset averaged over the period 2001-2010.

the ERA5 reanalysis which was shown to be a reliable, near-observed alternative for surface temperature while it also provides additional variables, not available in other types of datasets (e.g., gridded observations or satellite data).

The model output tends to overpredict maximum (TX) and underpredict minimum (TN) summer-average temperatures. Comparison of the ERA5 dataset with station measurements reveals that ERA5 underestimates TX (-1.7°C) and slightly overestimates TN ($+0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$) and, therefore, model biases are possibly lower. Maps of biases reveal quite notable differences among the three PBL schemes with regards to the magnitude and the sign. For TX, the ACM2 scheme shows warm biases throughout the simulation domain while YSU and MYJ have cold biases in sub-Saharan Africa and South Europe. For TN, ACM2 simulates the lowest TN with MYJ and YSU being warmer.

The performance of the three PBL schemes in simulating temperature extremes was also scrutinized. Model biases for the warmest day (TXx) index follow the spatial distribution that was observed in summer TX. Large positive biases ($>6^{\circ}\text{C}$) were found in areas with complex orography and coastlines with the ACM2 scheme showing the warmest biases overall. Colder biases were found for the warmest night (TNx) index with the sign and magnitude of model biases in each scheme strongly dependent on the geographic location. ACM2 is the coldest scheme mostly in the arid areas (biases exceeding 5°C) while it is warmer in southern Europe where YSU and MYJ are in good agreement with ERA5. Quite different spatial patterns of biases were found for the annual maximum of Heat Index (HIx), owing to the effect of the humidity, with MYJ being the warmest while ACM2 was found to be the coldest scheme.

Further interpretation of the model biases was achieved via the analysis of additional variables. Analysis of surface specific humidity showed the MYJ to be the wettest scheme and ACM2 the driest one. The MYJ wet biases can be attributed to weaker vertical mixing and entrainment, common in local closure schemes (Brown, 1996; Hu et al., 2010; Garcia et al., 2013). The YSU scheme is drier than MYJ, wetter than ACM2 and in better agreement with ERA5. These large discrepancies among the three schemes in sub-Saharan Africa could be linked to the model representation of the West African monsoon patterns Klein et al. (2015) and help explain the large differences regarding the simulation of TX that were noted before.

A qualitative estimation of the model entrainment has been obtained by inspecting spatial variations of the simulated PBL height. WRF overestimates the PBLH in most of north Africa and the Middle East suggesting stronger entrainment of warm and dry free-tropospheric air into the PBL, possibly due to the model warm bias in these areas. On average, ACM2 produces thicker PBLs than the other two schemes, consistent with the warmer temperature simulated

by the this scheme. On the other hand, MYJ, which is the coldest scheme, on average simulates lower PBLH as well. Vertical profiles of potential temperature and specific humidity show that colder schemes are predicting more surface moisture while they are drier at higher levels thus providing reduced transport of water vapour and weaker entrainment. This pattern is not applicable though to the profile over Saudi Arabia in which ACM2 is the driest despite being the coldest scheme, while over the Nile Delta the profiles in all schemes are warmer than ERA5 due to differences in the representation of land surface moist processes.

In this chapter we showed that model errors are dependent on the geographic location and on the variable being studied as different patterns were observed for maximum and minimum temperatures. Therefore, the performance of the different PBL schemes strongly varies according to the atmospheric conditions that prevail on the different regions within MENA and times of the day. Overall, the YSU scheme can be identified as the best performing scheme for the MENA-CORDEX domain. This is also evident from the quantitative analysis performed, in which YSU scheme shows higher scores of statistical metrics for most variables.

Chapter 6

Future heat stress with WRF model regional simulations

The work of this chapter is included in the following publication:

Ntoumos, A., Hadjinicolaou, P. , Zittis, G., Vautard, R., & Lelieveld, J. (2022). Severe heat stress in the Middle East - North Africa (MENA) region under different levels of climate warming. In preparation for submission in *Weather and Climate Extremes*.

6.1 Introduction

Heat extremes are expected to become more frequent and intense under global warming (Coumou and Robinson, 2013; Lewis et al., 2019). In the MENA region, climate projections indicate further intensification of heat extremes (Zittis et al., 2016; El-Samra et al., 2018; Legasa et al., 2020; Ozturk et al., 2021). In order to assess the future regional impacts of the extreme heat with higher accuracy, high-quality model projections are needed. High spatial resolution climate projections can be achieved through the use of regional climate models (RCM) for downscaling the outputs of GCMs (Giorgi and Gutowski, 2015). There is an growing number of studies applying future RCM projections for the MENA region (Bucchignani et al., 2018; Ahmadalipour and Moradkhani, 2018; Driouech et al., 2020; Ozturk et al., 2021). These regional climate studies are usually based on different forcing scenarios in order to investigate future changes which does not provide a direct link to the impacts of different global warming levels (Russo et al., 2017; Suarez-Gutierrez et al., 2020).

Apart from the dry heat, the combination of high temperature and humidity can be even more hazardous (Wehner et al., 2016) and pose an immediate threat to human health and survivability (Wang et al., 2022). Increased humidity can exacerbate heat impacts and lower

the thresholds in which temperature becomes deadly (Chen et al., 2019), lead to higher than normal hospital admissions (Goldie et al., 2017) and cause substantial loss of labor productivity (Mora et al., 2017; Orlov et al., 2019). Humid heat extremes are rapidly increasing worldwide (Rogers et al., 2021; Schwingshackl et al., 2021) and population exposure to humid heat is projected to increase faster than dry heat (Li et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2022). The usage of heat stress indices associated with high levels of air temperature and humidity is considered essential for estimating human-relevant threshold exceedances (Schwingshackl et al., 2021). From the wide range of heat stress indicators, the current study focuses on the analysis of the NOAA heat index (Rothfus, 1990; Steadman, 1979) and the wet-bulb temperature (TW). According to the latest IPCC report (IPCC, 2021), dangerous heat index levels ($> 41^{\circ}\text{C}$) are projected to become commonplace for a large part of the globe (including MENA), increasing by more than 100 days per year for a business-as-usual scenario. In Chapter 4, we showed that in MENA the heat index is projected to increase at a much faster rate than temperature related indices while several areas across the region may reach temperature levels critical for human survival. Wet-bulb temperature has been widely used to assess the effects of humid heat (Pal and Eltahir, 2016; Wang et al., 2022). Im et al. (2021) revealed that even before the middle of the 21st century, extreme TW temperatures, beyond the current climate variability, are projected to emerge in areas around the Mediterranean and in large part of the Middle-East. A TW of 35°C is considered to be the survivability limit (Sherwood and Huber, 2010), and prolonged exposure beyond this value could be lethal even for the fittest humans. The MENA region is highly susceptible to high TW values, especially in areas around the Gulf where humid heat events with $\text{TW} \geq 35^{\circ}\text{C}$ are projected by the end of this century (Pal and Eltahir, 2016). Therefore, considering that humid heat has not been yet widely explored (Rogers et al., 2021; Speizer et al., 2022), it is crucial to assess the projected levels of humid heat over the MENA region.

Considering these challenges, the present chapter examines the projected changes of magnitude and frequency of heat extremes over the MENA region at different global warming levels (GWL). For this, we apply the WRF model over the MENA-CORDEX domain at high resolution simulations for a reference period (1986-2005) and at three different periods corresponding to different GWL relative to the pre-industrial levels (2°C , 3°C and 4°C). This work specifically aims to account for the combined effects of high temperature and humidity by analyzing the projected values of Heat Index (HI) and wet-bulb temperature (TW). Further emphasis is given to the exceedances of specific thresholds and the potential population exposure to them, as well as the sub-regional hotspots where the heat stress will approach the limit of human health

tolerance.

6.2 Methodology

6.2.1 Model set-up

In this part of the study, simulations are performed using the updated WRF model version 4.3.1 over the MENA-CORDEX domain while the horizontal resolution and the vertical levels over which the simulations are implemented remained unchanged as described in chapter 5 (24 km and 35 vertical levels). The model top is also kept at 30 hPa. The initial and boundary data are taken 6-hourly from the Community Climate System Model (CCSM4) (Gent et al., 2011) of version 1 of the Community Earth System Model (CESM1) (Hurrell et al., 2013). In Chapter 3 the CCSM4 has been ranked among the best performing global models for the MENA region and its climate fields used as lateral boundary conditions in the WRF downscaling are bias corrected for climate mean and variability according to Bruyère et al. (2015). The simulation domain covers the whole MENA-CORDEX domain as illustrated in Chapter 5. The employed model configuration is the same as the one used in Chapter 5, apart from the selection of PBL scheme. According to the analysis presented in the previous chapter, YSU scheme was found to be the best performing PBL scheme and it is used in our simulations.

6.2.2 Numerical experiments

The WRF simulations were performed for a control period (1986-2005) and three future 20-year periods corresponding to different GWL (+2°C, +3°C and +4°C). The CCSM4 historical (1850-2005) and scenario (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5, 2006-2100) runs were employed in order to define the changing GWL. For this, we used global mean surface temperature (GMST) from the CCSM4 model, defined as the annually averaged, global mean, near-surface 2m air temperature anomaly with respect to the "pre-industrial" period 1850–1899. For instance, the +2°C period is determined by the year when the 20-year running mean crosses the +2°C threshold. As illustrated in Figure 6.1, under the intermediate RCP4.5 scenario, the GMST reaches +2°C warming in the period from 2030 to 2049. We follow the same procedure for the +3°C and +4°C using RCP8.5 simulation since RCP4.5 simulations do not reach +3°C. The periods of +3°C and +4°C global warming are 2048-2067 and 2069-2088 respectively. Taking into account these estimations, the WRF model was applied to downscale the CCSM4 global climate simulations for the present climate conditions (1986-2005) and for the different GWL relative to the pre-industrial period.

Figure 6.1: Global mean surface temperature (GMST) anomalies evolution according to CCSM4 historical (black solid line), RCP4.5 (black dotted line) and RCP8.5 (black dashed) pathways. The horizontal lines (black dashed) indicate the +2°C, +3°C and +4°C levels with respect to the "pre-industrial" period 1850–1899 (grey shading). The periods of the CCSM4 downscaling are indicated by the shading (grey: historical; orange: +2°C; red: +3°C; purple +4°C, as described in 6.2.2).

6.2.3 Indices of heat stress

In order to examine extremes, we used indices based on daily maximum and daily minimum near surface temperatures (TX and TN). These are the Warmest Day and Warmest Night, defined as the maximum of TX (labelled TXx) and the maximum of TN (labelled TNx), respectively, in a year. We also examine the Heat Index (HI) and Wet bulb Temperature (TW) to account for the heat stress induced by the combined effects of high temperature and high humidity.

As already mentioned in the previous chapters, HI is calculated with multiple linear regression of temperature and relative humidity as input variables (Rothfus, 1990; Steadman, 1979). In order to obtain highly accurate results, sub-daily information, instead of daily mean values, may be employed to calculate the HI. Ideally, HI should be calculated instantaneously at the model time step, to allow deriving the daily maximum value as closely as possible. In our case, the model output variables were obtained every 6 hours and therefore HI was calculated at these model time steps. For the calculation of the daily TW we use an empirical equation developed by Stull (2011) which is based on air temperature and relative humidity and it is described in Chapter 2. As in HI calculation, we used temperature and relative humidity data

from the model output at four daily time-steps and the maximum daily TW was subsequently derived.

6.2.4 Statistical considerations

In this study, changes in 50-year return value events are examined. In order to quantify the return periods of rare extreme events beyond the reference period length (1986-2005), the generalized extreme value (GEV) distribution approach is employed to estimate the 1-in-50-year extremes (Coles et al., 2001). For this, we used the R package “extRemes” (Gilleland and Katz, 2016) to fit the GEV distribution to the indices of annual maximum values (e.g. TXx) over MENA and subsequently the 50-year extremes were estimated.

We applied the commonly used generalized extreme value (GEV) distribution (Jenkinson, 1955) which is defined as:

$$F(x; \mu, \sigma, \xi) = \begin{cases} \exp\left[-\exp\left(-\frac{x-\mu}{\sigma}\right)\right], & \xi = 0, \\ \exp\left[-\left(1 + \xi\frac{x-\mu}{\sigma}\right)^{-1/\xi}\right], & \xi \neq 0, \quad 1 + \xi\frac{x-\mu}{\sigma} > 0 \end{cases}$$

where μ is the location parameter, σ is the (positive) scale parameter and ξ is the shape parameter. ξ represents the behaviour of the distribution tail with a positive ξ resulting in a heavy tail distribution and a negative ξ in a shorter tail distribution. The GEV distribution is fitted to the 20-year block maxima for the four indices of extremes under investigation. For the estimation of the GEV parameters, the Maximum Likelihood (ML) technique is implemented (Prescott and Walden, 1980). The GEV-ML method was applied to the reference period (1986-2005) to approximate the 1-in-50-year extremes. Then the return periods of these extremes were estimated for different GWL. The return periods are computed as $20/n$, where n is the number of daily exceedances above the reference period extreme value in a 20 year period.

We also account for the statistical significance of the the projected changes in heat extremes by following the definition used in the IPCC’s Atlas of Global and Regional Climate Projections (IPCC, 013b). According to this, a change is considered significant when its signal is larger than the interannual variability. The interannual variability is derived directly from the calculation of the standard deviation for temperature.

The CCSM4 meteorological fields used as boundary conditions in our downscaling are bias corrected (Bruyère et al., 2013), however RCM biases remain, as shown in 6.3.1. The absolute threshold-based temperature indices analyzed in this study are sensitive to these systematic model biases and, therefore, bias adjustment (BA) methods are necessary in order to improve

the confidence in the projected extreme values. It has been shown that simple BA methods, such as simple scaling, provide similar results to more complex ones (e.g. empirical quantile mapping) in the correction of extreme heat indices (Iturbide et al., 2022). Hence, the projected heat extremes derived from our WRF simulations were calculated using the underlying model variables (TX, TV, RH) which were bias corrected according to their climatological departures from the ERA5 dataset (Hersbach et al., 2020).

6.3 Results

6.3.1 Evaluation of the historical simulations

Figure 6.2: Absolute biases of the WRF simulations relative to the ERA5 dataset averaged over the 1986-2005 period for the warm period (MJJJAS) mean maximum (top,left), minimum (top,right) temperature and relative humidity (bottom).

The WRF simulation biases relative to the ERA5 reanalysis are illustrated in the maps of

Figure 6.2. It appears that model biases vary according to geographical location while different spatial patterns are observed for different variables. The model overestimates TX in most of northern Africa (especially in Egypt) and the Middle-East with an average bias of 2°C - 4°C. Furthermore, WRF shows very good performance in south Europe while colder biases are observed in sub-Saharan Africa, where an overestimation of RH is observed as well. These biases in TX and RH can be linked to the model representation of the West African Monsoon (WAM) patterns (Klein et al., 2015). According to this study, the WRF simulations produced a lower fraction low and mid-level clouds that strengthens the monsoon due to the higher amount of incoming solar radiation and will lead to a northward shift of the WAM as also observed in our case. In the rest of the MENA region, simulations are relatively drier while weak wet biases are present in the mountainous areas which can be attributed to differences in the orography. Regarding TN, there is no clear pattern with the model simulation indicating mostly weak cold and warm biases depending on the region. Similar to TX, simulations are in good agreement with ERA5 for most locations around the Mediterranean basin, showing mostly weak cold biases (1°C on average). For the rest of MENA biases are much more spatially variable comparing to the TX simulation and are presenting weaker or negligible biases in areas with substantial TX overestimation. This enhanced spatial variability can be attributed to errors in the representation of nighttime temperature inversion in areas with complex orography (Garcia et al., 2013).

A quantitative analysis of the presented results shows that the percentage of gridpoints of the model domain with a good performance ($MAE < 2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) is at 64% and 80% for TX and TN respectively. For RH, 74% of the gridpoints show relatively low biases ($MAE < 10\%$). Overall, despite some notable biases in some areas (overestimation of TX and RH), WRF simulations are in good agreement with ERA5 in many areas of the MENA and thus provides a satisfactory representation (within the range of known RCM biases) of the region's mean climatic conditions.

Apart from the spatial representation of the main variables, quantile–quantile plots (q-q plots) have been used in order to compare the probability distribution of the two datasets and illustrate biases at different parts of the temperature and relative humidity range. In Figure 6.3, q-q plots have been computed for the whole MENA and three different subdomains (Figure 4.10) for the warm period (May to September) daily maximum, minimum temperatures and daily mean relative humidity. Maximum temperatures tend to show larger biases at the high quantiles of the temperature distribution and mainly for Sahara and Middle-East regions. Better model performance is observed in the Mediterranean region where weak warm biases are indicated. In the other regions, there is a good agreement for days with lower temperatures while signifi-

cant overestimation of warmer temperatures is observed (up to 4°C). Minimum temperatures seem to be underestimated for the lower quantiles, especially at the Sahara domain. On the other hand, for the warmest nights there is a good agreement between simulations and the ERA5 dataset. Regarding daily mean relative humidity, results differ depending on the region considered. In the Mediterranean region, simulations underestimate relative humidity for drier conditions while they are in better agreement in the upper quantiles. For the other two regions, significant wet biases are observed mainly for the upper part of the relative humidity distribution, especially over the Sahara region reaching 15%. These wet biases can be attributed to stronger moisture transport due to the northward position of the WAM in WRF simulations (Klein et al., 2015).

6.3.2 Changes in heat extremes

Figure 6.4 presents the changes relative to the 1986-2005 reference period for the warmest day and night of the year (TXx and TNx, respectively). The results generally show an intensification of heat extremes with increasing global warming with both indices indicating stronger increases in the northern part of the domain (South Europe) which is in line with previous MENA region studies (Lelieveld et al., 2016; Almazroui et al., 2021; Ntoumos et al., 2022). This more pronounced warming in the more temperate areas of South Europe could be attributed to future soil moisture deficits which will limit evaporation and further amplify heat conditions (Zittis et al., 2014b; Russo et al., 2019). The changes are considered statistically significant for most areas under a 2°C global warming scenario while for 3°C and 4°C warming we find significant warming throughout the region.

Regarding the TXx index, model simulations indicate that the projected TXx value increase follows the three escalating GWL. The most pronounced warming is observed for the northern part of MENA and especially in the Balkan peninsula where the projected warming surpasses 5°C for the 3 degree global warming scenario. For the 4 degree warming scenario, the WRF simulations indicate a strong north-south gradient with a warming up to 8°C in south Europe and 3°C - 4°C in most of Sahara desert and Arabian peninsula.

Stronger warming in the northern part of the domain is also simulated for the TNx index. Similar to the TXx index, areas around the Balkan peninsula are projected to warm faster showing an increase from 3°C for a 2°C global warming to 7°C for a 4°C global warming. However, additional climate warming "hotspots" are showing up in locations over the Middle-East (Gulf region, Iraq) and over the northern parts of Egypt (Nile delta). It is worth noting that global models are not always able to capture these hotspots (Lelieveld et al., 2016; Ntoumos et al.,

Figure 6.3: Quantile–quantile plots between the WRF output and ERA5, computed for spatial averages of the MENA region and three subdomains and for the warm period (MJJAS) for daily maximum, minimum temperatures and relative humidity.

Figure 6.4: Projected 20-year mean changes in the Warmest Day (TXx, left) and the Warmest Night (TNx, right) under different GWL displayed as differences (in °C) relative to the reference period (1986-2005) simulated by the WRF model.

2022) highlighting the added information gained in high resolution regional climate projections. The projected warming relative to the control period in these areas will surpass 5°C under an intense, 4°C global warming scenario. These areas are already exposed to very high nighttime temperatures (TNx > 33°C) and the projected warming will amplify heat stress conditions. As also shown in Table 6.1, in the Middle-East region the spatial averaged TNx index will exceed 35°C under 4°C global warming.

It is worth noting that, especially for the northern part of the domain, TXx and TNx values are projected to increase much faster than the global mean surface temperature (GMST). As indicated in Figure 6.1, the CCSM4 model shows an average GMST warming from the pre-industrial until the reference period of about 1°C. Therefore, the global mean warming between the reference period and the levels considered in this study is actually +1°C, +2°C, +3°C. For a 4°C global warming scenario, many regions in south Europe show a warming over 6°C indicating that heat extremes in these areas are warming at least two times faster than the GMST. A lower warming rate, closer to the global rate, is projected for a large part of the Sahara desert.

6.3.3 Projected humid heat extremes

We extend the analysis of heat extremes by presenting the projected values of Heat Index and Wet Bulb temperature in order to quantify the combined discomfort effect of temperature and humidity. The values have been bias-adjusted based on the model biases from the ERA5 of 1986-2005 climatology derived according to 6.2.4. A quantitative overview of the two indices in different parts of MENA can be found in Table 6.1.

Maximum of Heat Index

Figure 6.5 illustrates the spatial distribution of annual maximum of the Heat Index (HIx) in the MENA region for the reference period and for the three different GWL. It should be noted that in these maps the 20-year mean HIx is shown, so the HIx values can be higher in individual years. The colour scale has been adjusted in accordance with the thresholds defined by the NOAA HI classification¹, which is used for issuing heat warnings in the USA. HI values below 27°C correspond to low heat stress conditions while for HI>27°C, four HI thresholds are defined depending on the heat stress levels and the relevant impacts on human health. A HI around 27-33°C is classified as "Caution", 33-40°C as "Extreme Caution", 40-51°C as "Danger" and a HI>51°C as "Extreme Danger".

¹<https://www.wrh.noaa.gov/psr/general/safety/heat>

Figure 6.5: Spatial variation of the bias-adjusted mean annual maximum of the Heat Index (HIx) for the reference period (1986-2005) and under different GWL simulated by the WRF model. Note that an HI of 27-33°C is classified with Caution, 33-40°C with Extreme Caution, 40-51°C with Danger and $HI > 51^{\circ}\text{C}$ with Extreme Danger.

In the reference period (1986-2005), HIx values remain below the 40°C threshold for most areas in the northern parts of the domain and fall into the lower risk classifications ("Caution" and "Extreme Caution"). For the hot and arid areas of the Sahara desert and the Middle East, the simulated values of HIx are surpassing the 40°C threshold (defined as "Danger"), along the Gulf coastlines, HIx values above the critical 51°C threshold (defined as "Extreme Danger") are simulated. The areas of higher HIx thresholds are projected to expand significantly for higher GWL. On average, stronger increase of the HIx index are simulated in areas characterized by higher climatological values of relative humidity (Mediterranean, coastal areas of the Arabian/Persian Gulf and Red Sea), where a combination of high temperature and humidity can be achieved. For a 3°C GWL, areas in the northern parts of the domain (South Europe) will record HI values about one level higher in the heat warning scale, exceeding the 40°C threshold in most lower elevation areas. Particularly strong increases, over 10°C relative to the present climate, are projected for the areas around the Gulf for a 4°C GWL (Figure 6.6). These regions are already recording HIx values above the 51°C threshold, and extremely high HIx values (over 65°C) are projected for a stronger GWL. The "Extreme danger" zone is expanding significantly and, for a 4°C global warming, will cover most coastal and lower elevation areas in the Middle East. Secondary hotspots are also found in sub-Saharan Africa, around the Nile Delta and coastal areas of the southeast Mediterranean. Hence, densely populated areas (e.g. Cairo) are projected to experience extremely dangerous levels of HI.

Maximum of wet bulb temperature

As above, another important measure of humid heat is TW, of which the mean annual maximum (TWx) is plotted in Figure 6.7. In this case, although no specific warning scale applies, the colour scale was adjusted in order to facilitate the distinction of the most hazardous TWx levels. TWx values below 24°C can be defined as moderate (but not negligible) heat stress levels with $TWx \geq 27^\circ\text{C}$ to be considered as the threshold for dangerously hot conditions (Krakauer et al., 2020). In the current climate, TW usually peaks at 30°C, rarely reaching 31°C (Sherwood and Huber, 2010), and therefore a $TWx \geq 30^\circ\text{C}$ is considered extremely dangerous (Kang and Eltahir, 2018), and can be defined as the threshold for 'unprecedented heat events'. The upper level corresponds to a $TWx \geq 33^\circ\text{C}$ and approaches 35°C which is the limit for human survivability under well-ventilated conditions.

In the present climate (reference period), the highest values of TWx are simulated mainly in the coastal areas. TW values over 30°C are very rare events in the reference period and it is only recorded in a few coastal areas around the Persian Gulf. This area is susceptible to high

Figure 6.6: Projected temporally averaged changes in the mean annual maximum of the Heat Index (Hlx) under different global warming levels displayed as differences (in °C) relative to the reference period (1986-2005) simulated by the WRF model.

values of TW since is characterized by very high temperatures, extremely high SST's along with marine, low-level winds which transfer humid air masses inland and ultimately lead to high TW values (Pal and Eltahir, 2016; Raymond et al., 2020). On the other hand, in arid areas remote from large water bodies and at higher elevation, lower TWx values ($<27^{\circ}\text{C}$) are simulated. TWx is projected to rise substantially for increasing global warming. For a relatively modest 2°C GWL, values of TWx over 27°C will expand inland in the arid areas of the MENA, while many coastal areas of the Mediterranean are also projected to record $\text{TWx} \geq 27^{\circ}\text{C}$. Even more dangerous values of TW are simulated for stronger global warming. A widespread exceedance of the 30°C threshold is expected in the Gulf region for a 3°C GWL while some coastal areas will approach the lethal 35°C threshold. Furthermore, locations around the Nile delta including

Figure 6.7: Spatial representation of the bias-adjusted mean annual maximum of the Wet Bulb temperature (TWx) for the reference period (1986-2005) and under different GWL.

Table 6.1: Bias-adjusted values for different GWL. Values are displayed for the TXx ,TNx, Hlx and TWx indices spatially averaged over the MENA domain, and the Mediterranean (MED), Sahara (SAH) and Middle -East (MEA) subdomains. The subdomains are displayed in Figure 4.10. The \pm ranges indicate 1σ standard deviations of the mean.

Index	Warming level	MENA	MED	SAH	MEA
TXx	2 °C	43.4 \pm 0.4	39.0 \pm 0.6	45.4 \pm 0.6	45.8 \pm 0.5
	3 °C	44.8 \pm 0.4	40.7 \pm 0.9	46.9 \pm 0.6	47.0 \pm 0.6
	4 °C	46.0 \pm 0.5	42.1 \pm 0.8	47.7 \pm 0.6	48.4 \pm 0.5
TNx	2 °C	29.9 \pm 0.3	25.6 \pm 0.5	31.6 \pm 0.4	32.5 \pm 0.6
	3 °C	31.2 \pm 0.4	27.1 \pm 0.8	32.9 \pm 0.5	33.8 \pm 0.5
	4 °C	32.5 \pm 0.4	28.8 \pm 0.7	34.0 \pm 0.4	35.2 \pm 0.5
Hlx	2 °C	42.1 \pm 0.5	38.0 \pm 0.6	42.3 \pm 0.5	44.5 \pm 0.7
	3 °C	44.0 \pm 0.6	39.9 \pm 1.0	44.3 \pm 0.7	46.7 \pm 0.8
	4 °C	45.9 \pm 0.6	42.0 \pm 0.8	46.3 \pm 0.7	48.8 \pm 0.9
TWx	2 °C	25.1 \pm 0.3	24.5 \pm 0.4	24.5 \pm 0.4	25.3 \pm 0.6
	3 °C	25.9 \pm 0.4	25.4 \pm 0.4	25.3 \pm 0.4	26.3 \pm 0.7
	4 °C	26.7 \pm 0.4	26.2 \pm 0.3	26.3 \pm 0.3	27.1 \pm 0.6

Cairo, coastal areas of southeast Mediterranean and Cyprus are also projected to face extremely dangerous TWx values over 30°C for a stronger global warming ($\geq 3^\circ\text{C}$). These areas are also showing the greatest TWx increase relative to the reference period (Figure 6.8) possibly due to a projected increase of relative humidity along with the climate warming. For a 4°C global warming, areas in the Persian Gulf coastlines will have to deal with deadly humid heat waves with TWx approaching and even surpassing the 35°C limit, which is in line with relevant studies (Pal and Eltahir, 2016; Wang et al., 2022). Recent studies (Raymond et al., 2020; Vercellio et al., 2022) have showed that the limit of survivability can be well below 35°C, depending on the environment (humid or dry). For the northern part of the domain (South Europe), the WRF simulations indicate a widespread occurrence of TW $\geq 27^\circ\text{C}$ along the coastlines and in low elevation areas. This values can cause significant impacts given the fact that during the deadly European and 2010 Russian heat waves TW remained below 28°C (Raymond et al., 2020).

Figure 6.8: Same as Figure 6.6 but for the mean annual maximum of the Wet Bulb temperature (TWx)

Human population exposure to extreme humid heat

The total population that will be exposed to dangerous threshold exceedances is presented in Table 6.2. We used gridded global population projections that are available for the period 2000–2100 at 10-year intervals and are based on the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) (Riahi et al., 2017; Gao and Pesaresi, 2021). Among the five different pathways, data were taken from the SSP5 which projects MENA population to increase till 2050 and then slightly decrease till the end of the century (Zittis et al., 2021b).

Results are showing that in the reference period already over 150 million people (21% of the total population) are exposed annually to HI values over the 40°C threshold (defined as "Danger") highlighting the hot climatic conditions that historically prevailed in the region. Dangerous TW values are currently affecting a smaller number of people (about 20 million) whereas only

Table 6.2: Total MENA population (in millions) and the percentage of the total MENA population that is projected to be exposed to dangerous levels of HI and TW at least once a year for different GWL. Population projections were based on the SSP5 (“Fossil-fuelled Development—Taking the Highway”) which projects radiative forcing at levels as high as RCP8.5.

Index threshold	Warming level	Population (millions)	Population (%)
HI > 51°C	Reference period	0.8	0.1
	2 °C	21	2
	3 °C	39	3.5
	4 °C	60	5
HI > 40°C	Reference period	153	21
	2 °C	472	42
	3 °C	603	50
	4 °C	678	57
TW > 30°C	Reference period	1.5	0.2
	2 °C	5.5	0.5
	3 °C	16	1.3
	4 °C	32	2.8
TW > 27°C	Reference period	20	2.7
	2 °C	147	13
	3 °C	242	20
	4 °C	318	27

a tiny portion of the population are exposed to “extreme danger” TW and HI values (over 30°C and 51°C respectively). These numbers are projected to change substantially for increasing GWL. For a GWL of 2°C, almost half of the regional population (472 million) and almost 150 million inhabitants will be exposed every year to dangerous HI and TW values respectively. Beyond 3°C of climate warming, extremely dangerous humid heat events will start to affect a significant portion of the MENA population. For a 4°C GWL, 60 million inhabitants may be exposed to “Extreme Danger” HI levels while unprecedented values of TW (>30°C) will affect 32 million inhabitants at least once a year.

6.3.4 Return periods of heat extremes

In this section, we scrutinize how the frequency of extreme heat events, occurring once in 50 years in the reference period, is expected to change for +2°C, +3°C and +4°C GWL. This can be quantified by calculating the return periods in years. Return periods can be defined as the

inverse of the probability of an event exceeding a given value and in our case the 1-in-50-years extremes which were deduced from a GEV distribution (6.2.4). The box-and-whisker plots in Figure 6.9 summarize the return periods of 1-in-50-years events for all MENA region grid points over land for the different indices of extremes (TXx, TNx, Hlx, TWx) and for different GWL.

For a 2°C GWL we observe that extremes related to humid heat (Hlx, TWx) are projected to occur more often than dry heat extremes (TXx, TNx). Already at 2°C GWL, TXx and TNx values occurring once in 50 years are projected to occur every one to four years in most regions within MENA with the median return period at 2 years. On the other hand, humid heat extremes are projected to occur every year on average (median return period equal to one). At 3°C of warming, 1-in-50-years extremes are expected to occur at least once a year (inter-quartile range below the red line for all indices). Especially the extreme humid heat events (Hlx, TWx) are projected to occur several times in a year for the majority of grid points in MENA. For a strong 4°C GWL, index values that are considered extreme in the current climate, will become the new normal by occurring multiple times per year (over 10 days annually for most of the MENA).

6.4 Summary and Conclusions

This Thesis chapter analyzed the future extreme heat conditions over the MENA region under three different GWL. We have performed WRF simulations by downscaling, at 24 km, bias corrected projections from the CCSM4 global model. The analysis focused on four different indices including dry-heat indices (warmest day and night) and humid-heat indices (Heat Index, wet bulb temperature). Based on the GMST anomalies relative to the 1850-1899 pre-industrial period, four 20-year simulation periods were defined corresponding to the current climate (1986-2005) and warming levels of 2°C, 3°C and 4°C. Using the simulations output we determined the projected regional changes in the magnitude and frequency of heat extremes, derived the exceedances of particular heat stress thresholds and identified high risk regional hotspots of extreme heat.

The historical period evaluation showed that WRF adequately simulates the pattern of the warm period (MJJAS) mean maximum and minimum temperatures as well as relative humidity. However, and despite the bias corrected forcing fields, model biases exist (Kim et al., 2021), being dependent on the geographical location and on the variable being studied. Stronger biases are observed for maximum temperature in parts of northern Africa and the Middle-East where model simulations overestimate temperatures by 2°C - 4°C. In addition, strong wet bi-

Figure 6.9: Box-and-whisker plots of return periods of extreme warm season (MJJAS) indices at different GWL for the MENA domain. Return periods of reference period (1986-2005) 1-in-50-years events for the TXx (top, left) TNx (top, right), Heat Index (bottom, left) and Wet Bulb Temperature (bottom, right). The red horizontal line indicates that 1-in-50-years extremes will occur every year.

ases can be found in sub-Saharan Africa. Overall, the WRF model shows better performance in simulating temperatures and relative humidity in south Europe where small biases are found as well for most regions in the minimum temperature simulation. A subsequent climatological mean bias correction of the TX, TN and RH variables allowed to calculate bias-adjusted indices of dry and humid heat extremes.

Analysis of the temperature-based extremes (TXx, TNx) indicated statistically significant warming for most regions within the MENA even under a 2°C GWL. A consistent pattern is revealed with stronger warming in the northern part of the MENA, up to 8°C for a 4°C GWL. For the TNx index, apart from the strong warming in northern MENA, substantial warming (>5°C under the warmest scenario) is projected for the already heat-stressed areas of the Arabian/Persian Gulf and Egypt. It is concluded that temperature extremes in most areas of MENA are expected to warm up to two times faster than the GMST.

The future levels of hot and humid conditions were quantified through the analysis of the Heat Index and wet bulb temperature. WRF projects that, for warming levels beyond 2°C, the 40°C threshold (defined as "Danger") is exceeded in many areas of South Europe where the index remains below that threshold in the current climate. Results also indicate a substantial expansion of the "Extreme danger" zone (HI >51°C) with increasing GWL. At 4°C GWL, extremely dangerous heat index values can be expected, apart from the greater region of Gulf and Arabian peninsula, in densely populated coastal areas of the southeast Mediterranean. Regarding wet-bulb temperatures, only few locations in the Persian Gulf are recording values over 30°C in the current climate. For a 3°C warming, simulations are predicting a widespread exceedance of the extremely dangerous 30°C TW threshold not only along the Gulf, but also in coastal areas of the Red Sea and the Mediterranean (e.g. Nile delta, Cyprus). In a scenario of 4°C GWL, coastal areas of the Gulf region are projected to experience deadly humid heat conditions, reaching the 35°C survivability threshold on an annual basis. Moreover, regional population estimations revealed that the MENA inhabitants that will be exposed to dangerous levels of heat stress are projected to increase sharply with climate warming. It is projected that for 3°C GWL, half of the future total MENA population (> 600 million) will be exposed to dangerous HI values (HI >40°C) at least once a year.

Finally, the frequency of very extreme events, that occur on average once every 50 years in the reference period, were analyzed for the three GWL. Our results show that humid-heat extremes (HI and TW) increase more in frequency than the dry-heat extremes (TXx, TNx). Even for a modest 2°C GWL, 1-in-50-years humid-heat events will occur annually for a large part of the MENA while dry-heat extremes are projected to occur a every few years on average. For

stronger global warming ($\geq 3^{\circ}\text{C}$), these 1-in-50-years extremes are projected to occur multiple times in a year over most of MENA region.

Chapter 7

Conclusions and future outlook

7.1 Conclusions

The intensification of heat extremes is expected to be particularly pronounced in the the Middle East – North Africa (MENA) region, enhancing the already hot and dry environmental conditions (Zittis et al. (2022) and references therein). Motivated by the need for improved regional climate change information, this PhD Thesis offered a thorough assessment of the increasing air temperature extremes over the MENA region under the changing climate, using global model data and by carrying out high-resolution regional climate model simulations. Initially, an ensemble of 18 global climate models was utilized in order to derive and analyze indices of extremes for the recent past and for different RCP scenarios. Then, the WRF model was optimized and applied over the MENA-CORDEX domain in (higher than existing output) 24 km resolution regional scale experiments. The main outcomes of the present study are summarized in the following paragraphs.

Assessment of the recent past temperature extremes from CMIP5 model data: I assessed the evolution of temperature extremes in the Middle East–North Africa (MENA) region and evaluated the performance of global climate model simulations for the past four decades (1980–2018). The indices of extremes were derived combining historical (1950–2005) and scenario runs (2006–2018 under RCP 2.6, RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5) and thus providing a "post-historical" record to retrospectively assess the RCP generation projections (Hausfather et al., 2020). In general, the CMIP5 model results showed a domain-wide strong, statistically significant warming, while the observation based ones were more spatially variable. The multi-model ensemble captured quite well the climatology of the hottest areas in the western parts of northern Africa and the Gulf region with the the warmest day (TXx) $> 46^{\circ}\text{C}$ and warmest night (TNx) $> 33^{\circ}\text{C}$, as well as the historical interannual variability. The comparison with reanalyses and

observational datasets revealed systematic biases in areas with complex orography due to GCM's coarse horizontal resolution. The multi-model analysis also revealed a MENA region average warming trend of $0.4 - 0.8^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{decade}$ for TXx and TNx, around $0.1 - 0.2^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{decade}$ than in observations.

I also separately assessed the performance of each model in order to reveal the best performing ones that could be used as boundary conditions for the MENA downscaling with the WRF model in Chapter 6 and more broadly for regional climate studies in the region. I found that most models simulate the 1980-2018 climatology reasonably well except for some outlying ones for the TXx index (MIROC-ESM, MIROC-ESM-CHEM, CanESM2). The MRI-CGCM3, CCSM4 and CSIRO_Mk3.6.0 were identified as the best performing. Regarding decadal trends simulation, most models overestimate the average MENA region warming rate with CCSM4, MRI-CGCM3 and CNRM-CM5 being closer to observations.

Future maximum heat conditions using CMIP5 data: Data were taken from 18 CMIP5 models to analyze the projected heat extremes over the Middle-East–North Africa (MENA) region until the end of the twenty-first century. Findings for a high emissions pathway indicated an excessive warming of more than 8°C in the northern part of the domain (south Europe) for the annual warmest day (TXx) and night (TNx). In the hottest parts of the domain (especially parts the Persian Gulf and Iraq) record high temperatures reached 50°C in the recent past, could even surpass 56°C by the end of the century and exceed the currently occurring worldwide records (Matthews, 2020), while temperatures over 50°C are expected to occur in a large part of the MENA region. Moreover, extremely high nighttime temperatures over 35°C are expected to occur in large part of the region. For the period of 2071–2100, excessive hot days ($\text{TX} > 40^{\circ}\text{C}$) and nights ($\text{TN} > 30^{\circ}\text{C}$) will become a part of the new climate normal in large parts of the MENA with some locations expected to exceed these thresholds on 180 and 120 days, respectively. Finally, calculations of the corresponding annual maximum of heat index (HIx) suggested that HIx is projected to increase at a much faster rate than temperature-based indices. Several areas across the MENA region may reach heat index levels ($> 51^{\circ}\text{C}$) that are critical for the human survival.

Effect of PBL parameterizations on WRF performance - best performing PBL scheme: Before carrying out long-term climate simulations, it is of high importance to identify a suitable combination of physics parameterizations. For this, the WRF performance in simulating summer air temperatures and heat extremes was analyzed by assessing its sensitivity to the use

of three PBL schemes (MYJ, YSU, ACM2) in multi-year simulations at 24 km horizontal resolution. The comparison with the ERA5 dataset indicated that simulations tend to overestimate maximum (TX) underestimate minimum (TN) temperatures while model biases strongly vary according to geographic area, with simulations showing good performance in some regions and substantial biases in others. Analysis of different variables like PBL height, moisture and heat fluxes showed that differences among the schemes can be linked to differences in vertical mixing strength and entrainment of air from above the PBL. The MYJ scheme was found to be the wettest and coldest scheme which can be attributed to weaker vertical mixing and entrainment of warm and dry free-tropospheric air into the PBL. The opposite holds true for the ACM2 scheme while the YSU scheme was in better agreement with ERA5. On average, the YSU scheme was identified as the best performing scheme for the MENA-CORDEX domain which is also evident from the statistical evaluation performed. Overall, in this part of the Thesis I found that the performance of the different PBL schemes strongly varies according to the atmospheric conditions that prevail on the different regions within MENA and this must be considered when selecting a suitable model configuration for sub-regional climate modelling studies.

Heat stress under different levels of global warming using 24km WRF simulations: High resolution multi-decadal simulations were carried out in order to assess the future heat stress conditions in MENA under 2°C, 3°C and 4°C of global warming relative to the pre-industrial period. Analysis of the projected changes of TXx and TNx indices revealed a stronger warming rate in the northern part of the Mediterranean basin, up to two times faster than the global average. In this part of the simulation domain, a warming up to 8°C in TXx index is anticipated for a 4°C of global warming. For the same level of global warming, extremely high nighttime temperatures are expected in several vulnerable areas of the Middle-East with simulations predicting a substantial warming (>5°C) for the TNx index.

The projected extreme heat stress conditions were quantified via the estimations of the Heat Index (HI) and wet bulb temperatures (TW). The areas affected by extremely dangerous HI values (>51°C) are expected to substantially expand for increasing global warming and will occur, apart from the greater region of Gulf and Arabian Peninsula, in densely populated coastal areas of the southeast Mediterranean. Regarding TW, at the 3°C of global warming, extremely high TW temperatures (>30°C), which are considered exceptionally rare in the current climate (Sherwood and Huber, 2010), are expected to be exceeded in a significant part of the MENA region (including coastal areas of the southeast Mediterranean and Cyprus). As for a 4°C global

warming, the survivability threshold of 35°C was projected to be overshoot mainly along the Arabian Gulf coastlines. Finally, analysis of the 1-in-50-years extremes return periods showed that even for a 2°C of global warming these extremes will occur every few years while they will become common-pace for higher levels of global warming.

Overall, this last part of the Thesis highlighted the MENA region as a climate change hotspot. Extreme humid-heat events are expected to exacerbate the impacts caused by extreme temperatures as most of MENA regions will have to deal with unprecedented humid-heat conditions. Findings underlined the necessity to limit global warming to 2°C in order to avoid devastating impacts in regional climate change hotspots like MENA. Heat stress impacts are projected to be particularly severe for stronger global warming (+3°C,+4°C) with several locations in the MENA being exposed to deadly heat conditions that will challenge social systems in the region (Waha et al., 2017).

7.2 Future Outlook

Analysis of extreme precipitation indices and trends: The present PhD Thesis focused on the analysis of temperature extremes in the MENA region and, therefore, further exploitation of the existing model data may include an analysis of precipitation trends and changes in precipitation extremes. As shown in the present Thesis and in other similar studies (Lelieveld et al., 2016; Zittis et al., 2019), the projected warming is characterized by high robustness and significance, while in the precipitation projections significant uncertainties remain (Zittis et al., 2021a). Estimation of precipitation trends are mixed, with many studies suggesting decreasing trends over the MENA region (e.g Zittis et al. (2022) and references therein) while the magnitude and significance of these trends strongly vary with some studies even showing positive trends for certain locations (Nelli et al., 2021; Cherif et al., 2021). Although future projections are showing an average 10-20% decrease by the end of the 21st century (Zittis et al., 2022), there is a strong evidence that extreme precipitation events are projected to increase in the region (Chen et al., 2014; Zittis et al., 2021a). A future research direction could address similar questions by using the available high resolution model output in order to assess the precipitation trends and extremes (e.g. indices related to heavy precipitation events or droughts) for different regions within MENA.

WRF simulations uncertainties and new downscaling experiments:

The analysis presented in Chapter 6 was based on single model simulations. Thus, an ad-

ditional research direction would address the projections uncertainty by comparing the WRF model results with other MENA-CORDEX models. In recent years, the CORDEX initiative (Giorgi and Gutowski, 2015) offered a new set of higher resolution simulations that contribute to better quality climate projections. Zittis et al. (2021b) assessed the future heatwave conditions using a multi-model ensemble of ten MENA-CORDEX downscaling simulations at 50 km, combining six global earth system models and four regional climate models. Results that were presented in Chapter 6, can be compared with this multi-model ensemble in order to better quantify the projections uncertainties, investigate the possible added value of our simulations and provide more statistically confident regional projections.

Another research direction could involve new downscaling experiments. In the most recent IPCC report (AR6) (IPCC, 2021), the latest generation (CMIP6) of global models became available. The CMIP6 models utilize the latest scenarios, namely Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) (Eyring et al., 2016). Compared to RCP-driven projections, the SSP-driven CMIP6 models revealed a slightly warmer temperature response mainly in the higher emission pathways (Iturbide et al., 2022; Cos et al., 2022) whereas global warming levels since pre-industrial times, are exceeded earlier in the results of the CMIP6 models (Tebaldi et al., 2021). Therefore, the WRF model could be used to downscale global fields from the new CMIP6 model output also in the framework of MENA-CORDEX activities. The current results of the CMIP5 models downscaling could then be compared with the new CMIP6-driven simulations.

Heat events drivers and processes:

The present study focused on the analysis of multi-decadal global and regional model outputs in order to investigate the long-term climate changes in the MENA region according to different emission scenarios. Further research could account for additional drivers of heat extremes (e.g. quantifying the role of future large-scale circulation changes), as well as to explore the underlying physical mechanisms and feedbacks of heatwaves. In Chapter 5 I showed that the selection of PBL parameterizations are affecting model biases regarding heat extremes. In a study of the most recent European "mega-heatwaves" (in 2003 and 2010), Miralles et al. (2014) explored the physical processes underlying these extreme heatwaves and found that the progressive heat accumulation in the atmospheric boundary layer led to further escalation in air temperatures. Thus, in addition to long term studies further research would focus on the analysis of individual extreme events and their driving mechanisms.

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Appendix A

Chapter 3

Table A.1: Final ranking of overall performance of the 18 CMIP5 global models with their respective average ranking as described in the text.

Models	Average ranking	Final ranking
CCSM4	6.61	1
CNRM-CM5	6.78	2
CSIRO_Mk3.6.0	6.94	3
MRI-CGCM3	7.43	4
BCC-CSM1.1	7.47	5
MPI-ESM-LR	7.76	6
MIROC-ESM	8.62	7
GFDL-ESM2M	9.23	8
GFDL-ESM2G	9.27	9
IPSL_CM5A-MR	9.6	10
BNU-ESM	9.69	11
HadGEM2-AO	9.92	12
CanESM2	10.26	13
MIROC5	10.64	14
MIROC-ESM-CHEM	10.96	15
GFDL-CM3	12.9	16
IPSL-CM5A-LR	12.92	17
HadGEM2-ES	13.99	18

Appendix B

Chapter 4

	MENA			
	TXx	TNx	Hot days	Hot nights
RCP2.6	1.9 ± 0.7	1.8 ± 0.7	20 ± 7	7 ± 5
RCP4.5	3.4 ± 0.8	3.2 ± 0.9	37 ± 10	17 ± 11
RCP8.5	6.4 ± 1.0	6.5 ± 1.1	73 ± 15	54 ± 20

	Mediterranean			
	TXx	TNx	Hot days	Hot nights
RCP2.6	2.4 ± 1.0	2.1 ± 0.8	4.9 ± 3.8	1 ± 1
RCP4.5	4.2 ± 1.1	3.5 ± 1.0	10.0 ± 6.4	2 ± 2
RCP8.5	7.8 ± 1.5	6.9 ± 1.4	28 ± 14.5	14 ± 14

	Sahara			
	TXx	TNx	Hot days	Hot nights
RCP2.6	1.8 ± 0.6	1.8 ± 0.7	23 ± 8	6 ± 4
RCP4.5	3.2 ± 0.7	3.3 ± 0.8	42 ± 11	20 ± 14
RCP8.5	6.2 ± 1.0	6.7 ± 1.2	84 ± 16	60 ± 26

	Middle-East			
	TXx	TNx	Hot days	Hot nights
RCP2.6	2.0 ± 0.7	1.9 ± 0.8	24 ± 9	12 ± 8
RCP4.5	3.5 ± 0.8	3.4 ± 0.9	41 ± 13	27 ± 14
RCP8.5	6.7 ± 1.1	6.8 ± 1.2	74 ± 16	68 ± 23

Figure B.1: Multi-model average changes over the time period 2081–2100 relative to the reference period (1981–2000) for different RCP scenarios and subdomains. The ranges indicate 1σ standard deviations of the mean.